

FLOATECH

D2.2. Validation Report of QBlade-Ocean

DATE OF DELIVERY - 31/08/2022

AUTHORS – SEBASTIAN PEREZ-BECKER, JOSEPH SAVERIN,
ROBERT BEHRENS DE LUNA, FRANCESCO PAPI, CYRIL
COMBREAU, MARIE-LAURE DUCASSE, DAVID MARTEN,
ALESSANDRO BIANCHINI

TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITÄT BERLIN, UNIVERSITY OF
FLORENCE, SAIPEM S.A.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101007142

FLOATECH
THE FUTURE OF FLOATING WIND TURBINES

Document track details

Project acronym	FLOATECH
Project title	Optimization of floating wind turbines using innovative control techniques and fully coupled open-source engineering tool
Starting date	01.01.2021
Duration	36 months
Programme	H2020-EU.3.3.2. - Low-cost, low-carbon energy supply
Call identifier	H2020-LC-SC3-2020-RES-RIA
Grant Agreement No	101007142

Deliverable Information	
Deliverable number	D2.2
Work package number	WP2
Deliverable title	Validation report of the new integrated aero-hydro-servo-elastic simulation framework QBlade-Ocean
Lead beneficiary	Technische Universität Berlin
Authors	Sebastian Perez-Becker (PB), Joseph Saverin (JS), Robert Behrens de Luna (BdL), Francesco Papi (FP), Cyril Combreau, Marie-Laure Ducasse, David Marten, Alessandro Bianchini (AB)
Due date	31.08.2022
Actual submission date	31.08.2022
Type of deliverable	Report
Dissemination level	Public

Version management

Document history and validation			
Version	Name	Date	Comment
V 0.1	TUB: PB, BdL, JS. UniFi: FP	15/07/22	First draft
V 0.2	TUB: PB, BdL, JS. UniFi: FP, AB	17/08/22	Compilation of all sections and proofreading
V 1.1	ECN: Bonnefoy, Aubrun TUD: van den Berg	26/08/22	Revision by external reviewers

All information in this document only reflects the author's view. The European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Background: about the FLOATECH project

The FLOATECH project is a Research and Innovation Action funded by the European Union's H2020 programme aiming to increase the technical maturity and the cost competitiveness of floating offshore wind (FOW) energy. This is particularly important because, due to the limitations of available installation sites onshore, offshore wind is becoming crucial to ensure the further growth of the wind energy sector.

The project is implemented by a European consortium of 5 public research institutions with relevant skills in the field of offshore floating wind energy and 3 industrial partners, two of which have been involved in the most recent developments of floating wind systems.

The approach of FLOATECH can be broken down into three actions:

- The development, implementation and validation of a user-friendly and efficient design engineering tool (named QBlade-Ocean) performing simulations of floating offshore wind turbines with an unseen combination of aerodynamic and hydrodynamic fidelity. The advanced modelling theories will lead to a reduction of the uncertainties in the design process and an increase in turbine efficiency.
- The development of two innovative control techniques (i.e. Active Wave-based feed-forward Control and the Active Wake Mixing) for floating wind turbines and floaters, combining wave prediction and anticipation of induced platform motions. This is expected to improve the performance of each machine and to minimize wake effects in floating wind farms, leading to a net increase in the annual energy production of the farm.
- The economic analysis of these concepts to demonstrate qualitatively and quantitatively the impact of the developed technologies on the levelized cost of energy (LCOE) of FOW technology.

In addition to the technological and economic impacts, the project is expected to have several impacts at societal, environmental and political levels, such as: public acceptance due to reduced noise and visibility issues of FOWT; very low impact on biodiversity and wildlife habitat because no piles are needed to be installed into the seabed; design choices requiring less material and space; the promotion of the installation of FOW in transitional water depths (30-50 meters), as the costs for FOW at those locations will become more competitive compared to the fixed bottom foundations.

Table of contents

Table of Contents

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	7
REFERENCES	7
1. INTRODUCTION	8
1.1. CONTEXT WITHIN FLOATECH	8
1.2. REPORT STRUCTURE	8
2. DESCRIPTION OF THE AERO-HYDRO-SERVO-ELASTIC TOOLS	9
2.1. QBLADE-OCEAN	10
2.2. OPENFAST	11
2.3. DEEPLINES WIND	12
2.4. CHAPTER REFERENCES	12
3. VALIDATION RESULTS FOR THE OC5 5MW FLOATING WIND TURBINE	14
3.1. DESCRIPTION OF THE TURBINE MODEL	14
3.2. DESCRIPTION OF THE LOAD CASES	17
3.3. RESULTS OF THE STATIC TEST	18
3.4. RESULTS OF THE DECAY TEST	19
3.5. RESULTS OF A FIXED TURBINE WITH WIND	22
3.6. RESULTS WITH REGULAR WAVES AND NO WIND	23
3.7. RESULTS WITH IRREGULAR WAVES AND NO WIND	26
3.8. RESULTS WITH IRREGULAR WAVES AND TURBULENT WIND	30
3.9. SUMMARY	34
3.10. CHAPTER REFERENCES	36
4. VALIDATION RESULTS FOR THE SOFTWIND 10 MW FLOATING WIND TURBINE	37
4.1. DESCRIPTION OF THE EXPERIMENT	37
4.2. DESCRIPTION OF THE NUMERICAL MODELS	40
4.3. DESCRIPTION OF THE LOAD CASES	42
4.4. RESULTS OF THE DECAY TEST	44
4.5. RESULTS OF THE AERODYNAMIC COMPARISONS	49
4.6. RESULTS WITH REGULAR WAVES AND CONSTANT WIND	51
4.7. RESULTS WITH IRREGULAR WAVES AND TURBULENT WIND	55
4.8. SUMMARY	63
4.9. CHAPTER REFERENCES	65
5. VALIDATION RESULTS FOR THE DTU 10 MW RWT WITH THE HEXAFLOAT SUBSTRUCTURE	67
5.1. DESCRIPTION OF THE TURBINE MODEL	67
5.2. DESCRIPTION OF THE LOAD CASES	69
5.3. RESULTS OF THE STATIC AND DECAY TESTS	69

5.4.	RESULTS WITH REGULAR WAVES AND CONSTANT WIND _____	73
5.5.	RESULTS WITH IRREGULAR WAVES AND TURBULENT WIND _____	78
5.6.	SUMMARY _____	88
5.7.	CHAPTER REFERENCES _____	89
6.	CONCLUSIONS _____	90
6.1.	CHAPTER REFERENCES _____	93

List of acronyms and abbreviations

Acronym / Abbreviation	Meaning / Full text
ANCF	Absolute Nodal Coordinate Formulation
BEM	Blade Element Momentum method
CoM	Centre of Mass
CoG	Center of Gravity
CW	Counter Weight
DBEM	Dynamic-BEM
DoF	Degree of Freedom
DL	DeepLines™
DLW	DeepLines WIND
EF	Eigenfrequency
FOWT	Floating Offshore Wind Turbine
IP	In-plane
LCOE	Levelized Cost of Energy
LHEEA	Laboratory in Hydrodynamics, Energetics and Atmospheric Environment
LLFVW	Lifting Line Free Vortex Wake method
LPMD	Linear Potential Morison Drag
ME	Morison Equation
MSL	Mean Sea Level
MSWT	Marin Stock Wind Turbine
NREL	National Renewable Energy Laboratory
OF	OpenFAST
OOP	Out-of-plane
QB	QBlade-Ocean
QTF	Quadratic Transfer Function
RAO	Response Amplitude Operator
RNA	Rotor-Nacelle Assembly
RWT	Reference Wind Turbine
SIL	Software-In-The-Loop
UBEM	Unsteady BEM model
WP	Work Package

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report constitutes deliverable 2.2 of the FLOATECH project, funded under the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101007142.

For the detailed validation and verification of the capabilities of QBlade-Ocean in work package 2 (WP2) of FLOATECH, a detailed definition of the three considered models was recently presented in Deliverable 2.1 [1]. This document can be seen as a continuation of that work as the three aero-hydro-elastic models within QBlade-Ocean were thoroughly validated against experimental results and other state-of-the-art aero-servo-hydro-elastic simulation codes with complex load cases. As a first check, the models were validated in static and decay tests to assure that their natural frequencies and damping coefficients align. Secondly, regular and irregular wave only load cases were carried out to isolate the hydrodynamic response and quantify the hydrodynamic accuracy of QBlade-Ocean. Finally, combined irregular wave with turbulent wind load cases were analysed in order to obtain insight into the accuracy of QBlade-Ocean in complex load cases where aero-, hydro-, servo- and structural dynamics concurrently play a significant role. Of the simulated models, two include experimental validation: the upscaled 10 MW SOFTWIND experimental turbine mounted on a spar floater and the upscaled 5 MW OC5 experimental turbine mounted on a semi-submersible floater. Both models were additionally set up in the open-source software OpenFAST to, on the one hand, compare the performance of both software tools and on the other hand, as a preparatory step for a full-scale code-to-code comparison with the aim of uncertainty identification between the codes occurring later in WP2. The third model – the DTU 10MW Reference Wind Turbine mounted on the Hexafloat floater – is used for numerical validation against the established commercial code DeepLines Wind™ which was used during the design process of the floater by the company SAIPEM.

The present document includes results of a selected set of load cases that demonstrate the capabilities of QBlade-Ocean compared to experimental results and the considered numerical codes. Links to the updated QBlade-Ocean models as well as the OpenFAST model are provided in the relevant sections of each model

REFERENCES

- [1] Perez-Becker, S., Behrens de Luna, R., Aero-Hydro-Elastic Model Definition in QBlade-Ocean, Technical Report: Deliverable 2.1, FLOATECH Project, H2020-EU.3.3.2. – Low-cost, low-carbon energy supply EU project, 2022.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. CONTEXT WITHIN FLOATECH

This report summarizes the results of the validation of QBlade-Ocean (QB), which is the main part of Task 2.1 of Work Package 2. To cover a wide range of floating turbine designs, three different models were used during the validation. These are the 10 MW SOFTWIND turbine mounted on a spar floater, the 5 MW OC5 turbine mounted on a semi-submersible floater and the DTU 10 MW Reference Wind Turbine (RWT) mounted on the Hexafloat floater. These models are visualised in Figure 1. Each model represents a different approach to FOWT technology and it is essential that the aero-hydro-elastic capabilities of QB are successfully verified with such a broad range of designs. This ensures that QB can be used for different analyses of all types of FOWTs. This validation report also serves as the basis for an uncertainty reduction study that will be performed in Task 2.2 of WP2.

Figure 1: Turbine models investigated. OC5 (left), SOFTWIND (center), Hexafloat (right).

1.2. REPORT STRUCTURE

The report is divided into three main parts. The first part contains Section 2, which briefly presents each of the aero-servo-elastic tools that were used for the validation studies. The second part includes Sections 3 to 5 and presents the main results of this report. Each section describes the individual turbine models and the load cases that were used for the validation tests. In addition, each section presents the detailed validation results for each of the main load case groups: aerodynamic tests, decay tests, regular wave tests with constant wind and irregular wave tests with stochastic wind. The final part includes Section 6, where the main conclusions of this validation report are presented.

2. DESCRIPTION OF THE AERO-HYDRO-SERVO-ELASTIC TOOLS

The validation of QB was performed against both experimental test data and against established open-source and commercial software packages. In this section the three aero-servo-hydro-elastic tools used for the validation tests of the different turbine models are presented. The three software tools are: QBlade-Ocean, OpenFAST and Deeplines Wind™. The properties of the three solvers are briefly summarised in Table 1. A more detailed description of the individual codes is provided in the following sections.

Table 1: Overview of software tools.

	QBlade-Ocean	OpenFAST	Deeplines Wind™
Open Source?	Yes	Yes	No
Graphical user interface?	Yes	No	Yes
Distribution	Free online	Free online	Commercial
Structural model: Blades (MB- Multibody)	MB, Corotational formulation, Euler-Bernoulli beams.	MB, Modal reduction, Geometrically exact beam theory	MB, Corotational formulation, Euler-Bernoulli beams.
Structural model: Tower	Corotational formulation, Euler-Bernoulli beams.	Modal reduction.	Corotational formulation, Euler-Bernoulli beams.
Structural model: Substructure	Corotational formulation, Euler-Bernoulli beams. (floating, fixed bottom)	Craig-Bampton method (fixed bottom).	Corotational formulation, Euler-Bernoulli beams. (floating, fixed bottom)
Aerodynamics: On-blade	Blade elements. Multi-polar. Dynamic stall: \emptyset_{ye} , B-L, Gormont, ATE Flap. Tower model.	Blade elements. Dynamic stall: \emptyset_{ye} , B-L, Boeing-Vertol. Tower model.	Blade elements. Dynamic stall: \emptyset_{ye} , Risø, Boeing-Vertol. Tower model.
Aerodynamics: Rotor/wake	Unsteady BEM, Free-vortex wake, Vortex particle	BEM, Dynamic inflow. Free-vortex wake (OLAF)	Steady BEM, Dynamic Inflow.
Hydrodynamics	Full Morison approach, Lin. Potential flow. 2 nd Order QTF	Full Morison approach, Lin. Potential flow. 2 nd Order QTF	Full Morison approach, Lin. Potential flow. 2 nd Order QTF
Hydrostatics	Linear buoyancy, explicit buoyancy	Linear buoyancy, explicit buoyancy	Explicit buoyancy
Environmental: Wind field	Turbsim, Hub-height files.	Turbsim, Hub-height files.	Turbsim, Hub-height files.
Environmental: Wave field	Regular, Irregular (numerous spectra), Multidirectional, Imported	Regular, Irregular (numerous spectra), Multidirectional, Import as time series.	Regular, Irregular (numerous spectra), Multidirectional, Import as time series.
Controller formats	Bladed, TUB, DTU	Bladed	Bladed

2.1. QBLADE-OCEAN

QBlade-Ocean (hereafter QB) is a state-of-the-art multi-physics code, covering the complete range of aspects required for the aero-servo-hydro-elastic simulation of horizontal and vertical axis wind turbines. QB is under development at the Technical University of Berlin since 2010, and is conceived as a modular framework for multi-fidelity aerodynamic, structural dynamic and hydrodynamic solvers. QB is equipped with a comprehensive graphical user-interface that aids during simulation setup, visualization and results post-processing. Within WP1 of the FLOATECH project, QB was extended with the functionality to enable design and simulation of bottom-fixed or floating offshore turbine substructures and their hydrodynamic behaviour [1].

QB uses a Lifting Line Free Vortex Wake method (LLFVW) for aerodynamic calculations. In this method, the rotor wake is explicitly modelled through lagrangian vortex elements. This results in a more accurate and detailed spatial and temporal representation of the rotor induction, when compared to Blade Element Momentum (BEM) approaches, and fully resolves the velocity distribution behind the rotor. This allows assessment of the interaction of the wind turbine wake with downwind turbines, accurately accounts for the aerodynamics of oscillating floating wind turbine structures and explicitly resolves unsteady wind turbine wake dynamics. As an alternative with lower computational demand, the aerodynamics of horizontal-axis wind turbines can be simulated using an unsteady polar-BEM implementation.

QB models the structural dynamics using a multi-body formulation. The components of the multi-body model can be either point masses or rigid- and/or flexible Euler-Bernoulli beam elements in a co-rotational formulation. The structural model uses a co-rotational beam element formulation implemented within the multi-physics solver Project CHRONO [2]. This allows for the treatment of highly nonlinear deflections of beam elements. For floating offshore simulations, QB integrates cable elements in the absolute nodal coordinate formulation (ANCF) which is an effective way to model the nonlinear dynamics of complex mooring systems.

QB is also able to model bottom-fixed and floating offshore wind turbine configurations. It offers the possibility to calculate the hydrodynamic loads on the wind turbine's substructure either via potential flow theory, a Morison-equation based theory or a user-defined combination of the two. The integrated potential flow approach also includes the higher order slow drift forces obtained from quadratic transfer functions (QTFs). QB integrates with potential flow data from software such as the WAMIT, NEMOH, BEMUse or similar toolboxes.

A full report of the additional development of QB done within the FLOATECH project can be found in [1]. The QB user training manual can be found in [3].

2.2. OPENFAST

OpenFAST (hereafter OF) is a state-of-the-art multi-physics code, developed by the National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL) to model horizontal axis wind turbines. Like QB, the code is open-source and is able to model onshore and offshore wind turbines, both bottom-fixed and floating. All the calculations presented in this report are performed with OpenFAST v3.0.0.

To model aerodynamics, two models are available in OF, AeroDyn v15 and AeroDyn v14. In the current validation study, both tools are used depending on the testcase. In particular, the MARIN Stock Wind Turbine (MSWT) – a downscaled (1/50th) experimental model trying to replicate the performance of the NREL 5MW RWT – mounted on the DeepCWind semi-submersible floating platform (used for OC5) is modelled using AeroDyn v15 [5]. The wind turbine's wake induction is modelled using blade-element-momentum theory (BEM), with corrections for high thrust, tip and root losses and misaligned inflow. Corrections for dynamic stall are used, in the form of the Beddoes-Leishman dynamic stall model. Dynamic wake effects are modelled using the approach proposed by Øye [4]. This model is able to account for the fact that changes in blade induction do not apply instantly to the entire wake by applying a filtering procedure to the axial and tangential induced velocities at each blade section. By inducing a time-lag in the wake, time-varying induction changes due to rotor motion or varying inflow conditions can be more realistically modelled. The flow disturbance on the blades caused by the presence of the tower is modelled through potential flow and aerodynamic drag loads on the tower support structure are also modelled. The DTU 10 MW wind turbine mounted on the SOFTWIND floating platform is modelled using AeroDyn v14 [6]. While this aerodynamic model is older, and by NREL's own admission, deprecated, it is still present in the latest releases of OF. More importantly, this model was used in the software-in-the-loop experimental tests conducted at Ecole Centrale de Nantes. Using it should therefore allow for the best possible agreement with the experimental data. Root and tip losses and dynamic stall (Beddoes-Leishman dynamic stall model as implemented in AeroDyn v14) are accounted for. Tower effects, aerodynamic tower loads and dynamic wake are not considered in AeroDyn v14.

The floating support substructures are modelled as 6-DOF rigid bodies. Their interaction with the sea is computed using HydroDyn [7], OF's hydrodynamics module. Similarly to QB, hydrodynamics can be modelled using potential flow theory, a Morison equation approach or a mix of the two. For test cases presented in this report, potential flow theory is used, with the addition of the Morison equation to model quadratic drag. Regarding the potential flow solution, added mass, linear damping and wave-response coefficients are pre-computed in the frequency domain using an external potential flow solver, such as WAMIT [8]. Second order difference frequency forces can also be accounted for in OF. The structural dynamics are solved using a modal-based structural module, ElastoDyn [9]. The structural deformations are calculated as linear superposition of the pre-determined mode shapes, allowing for a very fast solution with limited degrees of freedom to solve for [10]. Moorings are modelled using MoorDyn [11], a dynamic lumped-mass mooring line model. The model accounts for internal

axial stiffness and damping forces, weight and buoyancy forces, hydrodynamic forces from Morison's equation, and vertical spring-damper forces from contact with the seabed.

2.3. DEEPLINES WIND

DeepLines™ (hereafter DL) is a commercial integrated software solution to perform in-place and installation analyses of various offshore structures, based on the finite element method. It allows for design of flexible risers, power cables and umbilical, pipelines, mooring systems, towed systems and simulations of marine operations. DL is part of the marine software solutions suite developed by Principia and IFP Energies Nouvelles. This numerical tool is based on the program Flexan, initially developed for flexible risers and used from 1980.

Since then, DL's field of application has been extended to perform conceptual, basic and detail design of different systems in the Oil & Gas industry: drilling risers, hybrid towers, bonded and unbonded flexible risers, offloading lines, fibre optical cables.

DL is also closely coupled with Diodore™, a diffraction/radiation solution. This allows calculation of the interactions between any floating unit and its mooring lines or risers. The mooring elements are treated as cable elements with purely axial stiffness without compression. External links with other diffraction/radiation software tools were also made possible. As with QB, the buoyancy forces are explicitly calculated with a discrete approach. DL can also handle vortex induced vibrations analysis, structural fatigue damage analysis, as well as line contact and soil interaction modelling.

To address the needs for an overall design tool raised by the development of offshore wind turbines platforms, a new module DeepLines WIND (hereafter DLW) was created in 2011. DLW is designed to perform fully-coupled dynamic finite element analysis. It accounts for combined effects of aerodynamic loads on the blades, active pitch control, hydrodynamic loads on the floating platform and dynamic moorings loads. Several BEM models are implemented in an external .dll library to calculate the aerodynamic loads. DLW is able to simulate both horizontal and vertical axis wind turbines. The aerodynamic model in DLW uses a BEM approach coupled with a dynamic inflow model. In this case no unsteady blade aerodynamics model has been applied.

2.4. CHAPTER REFERENCES

- [1] Saverin, J., Perez-Becker, S., Behrens de Luna, R., Marten, D., Gilloteaux, J.C., Kurnia, R., Higher order Hydroelastic Module. Technical Report: Deliverable 1.2, FLOATECH Project, European Union: H2020-EU.3.3.2. - Low-cost, low-carbon energy supply EU Project.
- [2] Tasora, A., Mazhar, H., Serban, R., Pazouki, A., Melanz, D., Fleischmann, J., Taylor, M., Sugiyama, H. and Negrut, D., Chrono: An Open Source Multi-physics Dynamics Engine. High Performance Computing in Science and Engineering, 19–49. doi:10.1007/978-3-319-40361-8_2, 2016. doi:10.1007/978-3-319-40361-8_2.

- [3] Saverin, J., Marten, D., Perez-Becker, S., Behrens de Luna, R., Training Manual, Project Partner Workshop and Public Dissemination. Technical Report: Deliverable 1.3, FLOATECH Project, European Union: H2020-EU.3.3.2. - Low-cost, low-carbon energy supply EU Project.
- [4] Snel, H. and Schepers, J., Joint investigation of dynamic inflow effects and implementation of an engineering method, Netherlands, 1995.
- [5] Murray, R., Hayman, G., Jonkman, J., Damiani, R., AeroDyn V15.04: Design Tool for Wind and MHK Turbines, United States. <https://dx.doi.org/10.15473/1415580>, 2017.
- [6] Jonkman, B., Jonkman, J., Dimiani, R., AeroDyn v14 - <https://github.com/old-NWTC/AeroDyn14>, online, last access 15.08.2022.
- [7] Jonkman, J., Robertson, A., Hayman, G., HydroDyn User's Guide and Theory Manual, NREL.
- [8] WAMIT User Manual Version 7.4, WAMIT Inc., Chestnut Hill, MA 02467-2504, USA, <https://www.wamit.com/>
- [9] Elastodyn Theory Guide and Users Manual. Readthedocs: <https://openfast.readthedocs.io/en/dev/source/user/elastodyn/index.html>. Accessed 10.08.2022.
- [10] Jonkman, J. "Overview of the elastodyn structural-dynamics module." NREL Wind Turbine Modeling Workshop, EWEA Offshore, Frankfurt, Germany. 2013.
- [11] Hall, M., MoorDyn User's Guide, NREL, United States, 2015

3. VALIDATION RESULTS FOR THE OC5 5MW FLOATING WIND TURBINE

This section presents the validation results of the 5 MW MSWT with the OC5 substructure, henceforth called 5 MW OC5 model. This FOWT was investigated in detail within the Offshore Code Comparison Collaboration, Continued, with Correlation (OC5) project [1, 2]. Thus, experimental data of a downscaled 1/50th model is publicly available together with a large database of other established aero-servo-elasto-hydrodynamic codes. It is therefore a case that allows a good categorization of differences one might obtain between experimental results from the wave test facility and the ones from the numerical simulation.

Even though experimental data is available and ultimately represent the reference for the simulation results of QB, a second model of the 5 MW OC5 model was set up in OF. This provides the opportunity to already start identifying differences caused by different modelling approaches. As the primary purpose of this work is the validation of QB, comparison to experimental results is prioritised, and the comparison to DLW was deliberately omitted for brevity. Furthermore, an existing model did not exist for this substructure and insufficient resources were available for the corresponding development. The results of both simulation codes will be shown, they however were not tuned to show the best agreement to each other but rather to replicate the experimental results.

Figure 2: Visualization of the 5MW OC5 FOWT model in QB in regular waves.

3.1. DESCRIPTION OF THE TURBINE MODEL

The complete description of the 5 MW OC5 model is given in a former deliverable of FLOATECH (D1.1) [3]. Figure 2 shows the FOWT model in a regular sea state. The QB model of the 5 MW OC5 FOWT is publicly available at the following location:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6397352>

It should be noted that the model found at the abovementioned location might slightly deviate from the model described in this document. This is because further numerical tuning might be necessary to better align results in the remainder of WP2. All versions and changes to the model will be documented at the DOI provided above.

The OF model was built to be as consistent as possible with the OC5 Phase II semi-submersible wind turbine definition [1, 2] and with the QB model described in [3]. Aerodynamics are modelled in AeroDyn v15 using blade element momentum theory (BEM). A dynamic induction model developed by Øye [4] is used to account for unsteady inflow effects. When coupled to BEM, we refer to the aerodynamic model as Dynamic-BEM (DBEM). Blade aerodynamic unsteadiness is modelled using a Beddoes-Leishman type dynamic stall model as implemented in OF (Minnema/Pierce variant) [5]. In agreement with standard industrial practices, corrections for root and tip losses, non-uniform non-aligned inflow and high induction are also included in the aerodynamic model. The blade aerodynamic definition in terms of chord and twist distribution as well as sectional lift and drag coefficients match those described in [6, 3]. Structural dynamics are modelled using a modal formulation in ElastoDyn. As specified in [2], only the tower is considered flexible while the blades are considered rigid. The tower mass distribution was defined to include the mass of the measurement cables so that the total tower mass matches the specification [2]. The mass distribution was defined such as to attempt to best match the centre of gravity of the floating subsystem. This parameter is not an output of the OF model however, therefore it was not possible to tune the system to match this parameter exactly.

As for hydrodynamics a LPMD approach is used: radiation and diffraction forces are modelled using potential flow coefficients, appropriately pre-processed in WAMIT [7] while quadratic drag is modelled using a Morison equation approach. Traversal drag coefficient is considered to be uniform on all the semi-submersible columns with a value of $C_d = 1.35$. This value is significantly higher than expected for similarly sized floating substructures and was tuned to ensure good damping characteristics were achieved in free-decay tests. An axial double-sided drag coefficient of 4 is applied to heave plates to account for viscous damping in heave motions. Additional linear damping is introduced through a linear damping matrix in HydroDyn, again to better match damping characteristics of the experimental model. Additional linear stiffness in surge and sway is also introduced to better match the natural period in these DOFs. The mooring system is modelled using a dynamic mooring model (MoorDyn). The mass and stiffness of the cables, as well as their hydrodynamic diameter are specified to match specification [2].

Throughout the validation on the 5 MW OC5 model, no controller was applied in accordance with the load cases performed in the wave tank facility. In load cases in which turbulent wind fields were included, constant prescribed values of blade pitch and rotor RPM from the OC5 experimental documentation were imposed on the rotor of the MSWT. For load cases in standstill condition, the azimuthal position of the rotor was set so that one blade was facing the ground and aligned in parallel with the tower (see Figure 2).

While the modelling choices in QB and OF are largely consistent, both codes were set up independently and particular care was given to use each tool to its fullest ability to represent the actual physical phenomena. In particular, the main differences can be listed as follows:

- In OF buoyancy is modelled as the sum of a constant buoyancy force, which depends on the volume of the submerged substructure, and a deviatory buoyancy force, which is calculated using a hydrodynamic stiffness matrix that models restoring forces that arise when the body is displaced. In QB, the hydrostatic buoyancy force is discretely calculated based on the displaced volume by the floating structure with respect to the mean sea level (MSL). Thereby, the volume of the partially submerged elements at the sea surface is calculated upon the intersection of the MSL and the centreline of the cylindrical element. This approach introduces an error since the assumption of a constant sea level along the horizontal extension of one of the large cylindrical elements of the OC5 platform is flawed. Therefore, the partially submerged cylindrical elements are discretized into 100 prismatic elements. The intersection of the MSL with the centreline position of each of these elements is now considered and the error thus minimized. This approach should yield improved results compared to the approach of OF as nonlinearities (e.g. for large pitch angles) are captured [8].
- The Wheeler kinematic stretching method is applied in QB to approximate the water kinematics above MSL. This method stretches the scaling term $E(z)$ ¹ during a crest and contracts it in a trough. Without the application of kinematic stretching, this scaling term is always referring to the MSL, neglecting the unsteady nature of the water kinematics caused by gravity waves. OF currently does not account for kinematic stretching [8].
- QB models aerodynamics using LLFVW theory, while Dynamic-BEM is used in OF. As discussed in [9], LLFVW theory is able to intrinsically account for relevant aerodynamic phenomena such as unsteady, non-uniform misaligned inflow, root and tip losses, dynamic wake, and high induction. While BEM models have been extended to include all of the mentioned phenomena, most of these models are untied to the underlying physics, and may not perform adequately if used outside of their range of validity.
- Structural dynamics are modelled with very different approaches. QB employs a multibody finite-element model based on Euler-Bernoulli beams, while OF uses a much simpler modal approach. As shown in [8, 10], QB is able to account for complex phenomena such as large deformations and asymmetric full system modes, while OF is not. Within the context of the 5 MW OC5 model, this does not influence the structural dynamics of the rotor as they are modelled as stiff structures [2].

¹ $E(z)$ defines the particle velocity distribution between the sea bed and the sea surface

The selection of sensors that were used throughout the validation process of this model is listed in Table 2. Besides the global DoFs of the structure (surge, heave, etc.), the tower base sensor is of particular interest since it represents the connecting node through which aerodynamic loads from the rotor and hydrodynamic loads from the floater are passed. From the three fairleads, it is Fair2Ten that aligns with the x-axis (wind direction). The second-order wave loads play a significant role for the OC5 platform as its low natural frequencies pose a risk of being excited by difference-frequency loads. Since sum- and difference-QTFs are openly available, a code-to-code comparison between QB and OF to validate the second order loads is feasible.

Table 2: Load Sensors for the 5 MW OC5 model validation.

Sensor Name	Description	Coordinate system
PtfmSurge	Platform Surge [m]	Global
PtfmHeave	Platform Heave [m]	Global
PtfmPitch	Platform Pitch [deg]	Global
TwrBsMyt	Tower Base Fore - Aft Bending Moment [kNm]	Global
Fair1Ten	Line 1 fairlead tension [kN]	-
Fair2Ten	Line 2 fairlead tension [kN]	-
Fair3Ten	Line 3 fairlead tension [kN]	-
WaveElev	Wave Elevation at Undisplaced position [m]	Global
C_p	Power Coefficient [-]	-
C_T	Thrust Coefficient [-]	-
WindVxi	Longitudinal Wind Speed (at hub height) [m/s]	-

3.2. DESCRIPTION OF THE LOAD CASES

A series of load cases varying in their complexity are defined to validate the modelling capabilities of QB. Since experimental data on the OC5 platform with the 5MW MSWT exist, it was decided to repeat a selected number of load cases performed in the MARIN wave tank facility [1]. A large set of data from multiple codes and, most importantly, experimental results can hence be used to categorize the performance of QB. The mooring tensions are analysed

in static tests and the model characteristics, such as natural frequencies and damping coefficients, in decay tests. Furthermore, to ensure good alignment of the models, isolated load cases focusing on wind or wave only loads are performed in order to separately validate the aerodynamic and hydrodynamic responses. Combined turbulent wind and wave loads represent the most complex cases. Table 3 lists all the considered load cases for the 5 MW OC5 model. The load case numbering corresponds to the one used by the OC5 consortium in [2]. These cases do not include the effect of an ocean current.

Table 3: List of load cases carried out within the OC5 code comparison collaboration [2].

Load Case Nr.	Description	RPM [1/min]	Pitch [deg]	Wind Condition	Wave Condition
LC1.2a	Static Load Traverse - Surge	None	0	None	None
LC1.2b	Static Load Traverse - Sway	None	0	None	None
LC1.4a-	Surge Decay	None	90	None	None
LC1.4b	Heave Decay	None	0	None	None
LC1.4c	Pitch Decay	None	90	None	None
LC1.4d	Yaw Decay	None	90	None	None
LC2.1	Windfield 1, turbine fixed	5.5 – 17	0.86	12.91 m/s; turbulent	None
LC2.2	Windfield 2, turbine fixed	5.5 – 17	15.0	21.19 m/s; turbulent	None
LC3.1	Reg. Wave 1;	None	90	None	H = 7.37 m, T = 12.07 s
LC3.2	Reg. Wave 2;	None	90	None	Hs = 9.41 m, Tp = 14.3 s
LC3.3	Operational Wave;	None	90	None	Hs = 7.1 m, Tp = 12.1 s, $\gamma = 2.2$, JONSWAP
LC4.1	Operational Wave; Windfield 1	12.1	1	12.91 m/s; turbulent	Hs = 7.1 m, Tp = 12.1 s, $\gamma = 2.2$, JONSWAP
LC4.2	Operational Wave; Windfield 2	12.1	17.2	21.19 m/s; turbulent	Hs = 7.1 m, Tp = 12.1 s, $\gamma = 2.2$, JONSWAP
LC4.3	Operational Wave; Dynamic wind 1	12.1	1	13.05 m/s; turbulent	Hs = 7.1 m, Tp = 12.1 s, $\gamma = 2.2$, JONSWAP

3.3. RESULTS OF THE STATIC TEST

Load cases LC1.2a and 1.2b aim to validate the definition of the mooring system. The floating structure is displaced from its neutral stand-still position (NP) and the loads that act at each

of the three fairlead connectors in x-direction (surge LC1.2a) and y-direction (sway LC1.2b) are summed up respectively to give the cumulative mooring loads. The results of the static test are displayed in Figure 3. Good agreement is observable between the experimental and both numerical models of the 5 MW OC5 FOWT. Even for large surge-displacements (more than 15 m), where the line connection points of each of the three mooring lines are displaced considerably, very close alignment with the experimental results is present. Between -15 m and 5 m almost perfect alignment is present. The same conclusion may be drawn for LC1.2b which displays very good agreement.

Figure 3: Comparison of the cumulative fairlead loads in X and Y direction – LC1.2a (left) and LC1.2b (right). Negative x-values indicate a displacement in wind direction.

3.4. RESULTS OF THE DECAY TEST

Figure 4: Natural frequency and damping comparison – LC1.4

The aim of the decay test load cases was the validation of the calibration of the model. Thereby, the six rigid-body natural frequencies and damping coefficients as well as the

resonance-critical first tower bending frequencies in fore-aft and side-side directions are extracted. The latter are presented in Table 4.

The natural frequencies of the six DoFs from both numerical codes and the experiment are displayed in the bar chart in Figure 4. It can be seen that very good agreement was reached. To validate the quadratic and linear damping terms, it was decided to not follow the route of the OC5 experiments, in which linear and quadratic damping coefficients were compared. This decision is based on the fact that, due to the regression analysis, both coefficients and in particular the linear damping coefficient are very sensitive to sampling rate and the peak identifying algorithms. Since a visual comparison of the time series offer insight into the quadratic damping (first peaks) and the linear damping (peaks at the end of the time series), it was decided to follow this approach. Experimental data of the decays was not publicly available but thanks to NREL, this information was shared upon request. Figure 5 displays the time series of the decay in the surge and pitch DoFs². Generally, good agreement of the time series may be obtained. The visual comparison of the damping yields that QB is overestimating the quadratic damping in surge and underestimating it in pitch direction. The linear damping aligns very well in both DoFs.

Figure 6 depicts the mooring loads at the fairlead connection points during the decay test in surge direction (LC1.4a). Unfortunately, time resolved data of this sensor from the experimental campaign was unavailable for this load case. As a reference, pretension values of each line provided in the summary document of the campaign [1] are plotted. After the oscillation damps out, both numerical codes should ideally converge to the pretension value. In comparison to each other, the OF and QB models agree well in amplitude and phase for each of the three lines. Especially in the case of line 1 and line 2, the mean value of the oscillation coincides with the pretension value of the experiment. Line 3 demonstrates a slight offset in its mean value compared to the pretension that is detailed in the report of the experiment. The difference however amounts to about 3% and can be considered acceptable. Potential causes for the deviation might be a hysteresis effect in the experiment that creates an offset in the equilibrium position of the structure depending on the previous deflection [2]. A change in the equilibrium position would presumably have an influence on the pretension values. Other possible causes might be uncertainties in the equivalent diameter or density of line 3 as the mooring line properties are not identical between the lines.

The tower natural frequencies of the experimental model of the 5 MW OC5 model are matched closely with differences below 5%. This agreement was achieved by considerable scaling of the stiffness parameters. The presumable cause for the need to reduce the stiffnesses by 25% may lie within the fact that the experimental tower consists of two aluminum rods that overlap at their connection point.

² To not distract the reader by small differences in the neutral position in comparison to structure size, the time series are offset by the mean value of the presented time series.

Figure 5: Time series comparison and damping evaluation in surge – LC1.4a (right) and pitch – LC1.4c (left) direction.

Figure 6: Fairlead loads during LC1.4a. Pretension of the experimental set-up in stand-still condition is indicated with the horizontal line.

Table 4: First tower natural frequencies of the 5 MW OC5 FOWT model.

Mode name	Value QB	Value OF	Value Experiment
First tower side-side	0.316 Hz	0.330 Hz	0.325 Hz
First tower fore-aft	0.331 Hz	0.327 Hz	0.315 Hz

3.5. RESULTS OF A FIXED TURBINE WITH WIND

Aerodynamic forces play a key role in the response of a FOWT. The goal of the aerodynamic tests presented in Figure 7 is to validate the aerodynamic predictions of the OF and QB models. The tests are performed by cantilevering the tower, removing any influence that platform motion may have. As shown in Table 3, in LC2.1 a wind field with approximately 5% turbulence intensity and 12.91 m/s mean is imposed, while in LC2.2 a wind field of 21.19 m/s mean and 5% turbulence intensity is used. For each point shown in Figure 7, a 20-minute long simulation is performed in QB and OF, respectively. C_p and C_t are computed and averaged to obtain the data points in Figure 6. The tip-speed ratio (TSR) is varied by increasing the rotor speed from 6 to 17 rpm.

Figure 7: Aerodynamic rotor performance of the MSWT in fixed conditions (LC2.1 and LC2.2)
Experimental data from [6].

The numerical models are compared to experimental data from [6] as no results for these test cases are available in the OC5 repository. Very good agreement is shown for rotor thrust for both load cases. Similarly, power coefficient is also in very good agreement in load case 2.2. For LC2.1 both OF and QB underestimate C_p between TSR 6 and TSR 7 and overestimate C_p above TSR 7. Overall however, the discrepancies are small. Moreover, the turbine operating point in the experimental tests is slightly below TSR 6, where very good agreement between numerical and experimental models is shown. Although a similar level of agreement between

numerical and experimental tests can be noted in [6], details regarding the experimental test procedure are absent. The fact that the lower fidelity BEM model of OF shows similar accuracy as the higher fidelity LLFVW model QB uses may be explained by the geometric properties of the 5MW MSWT rotor. The stiff blades and almost no out-of-plane prebend of the rotor make it align very well with the planar actuator disk assumption on which the BEM approach is based.

3.6. RESULTS WITH REGULAR WAVES AND NO WIND

Regular wave tests are analysed with the objective of demonstrating that hydrodynamic excitation in the wave frequency range is properly captured by the numerical models and to evaluate system response to waves in a simplified scenario.

In LC3.1 a regular wave with an amplitude of 7.37 m and period of 12.07 s is imposed. As opposed to a perfectly sinusoidal wave excitation, the external wave height time series that was measured in the wave basin during the experimental tests was used. As the waves in the experiment are not perfectly sinusoidal, higher-order harmonics of the dominant frequency are also excited. Using the basin-measured waves allows the introduction of this excitation in the numerical models as well. In Figure 8 the recorded time series of selected load sensors as measured in LC3.1 are shown: platform surge, pitch and heave to evaluate platform motion, fairlead tensions of the three mooring lines, and tower base fore-aft shear force (TB F_x) and fore-aft bending moment (TB M_y). As shown in Figure 8, when excited by a regular wave, the floating system responds linearly in terms of motions and fairlead tensions. In other terms, when excited by a harmonic wave, the system responds harmonically at the same frequency of the exciting wave. Overall, system response in amplitude as in phase shift with respect to the incoming waves is very good for both OF and QB in terms of motions and fairlead tensions. The mean values also appear to be captured very well by both numerical codes. Tower base fore-aft shear force (TB F_x) and fore-aft bending moment (TB M_y) show strong excitation at the tower resonance frequency. The tower resonance frequency of approximately 0.32 Hz happens to be very close to the third harmonic of the wave frequency. Because the waves generated in the basin are not perfectly harmonic, excitation close to the first tower fore-aft mode is present, thus explaining the behaviour observed in Figure 8. Both OF and QB are able to capture this effect but both codes overestimate the response at the tower natural frequency.

In LC3.2 a regular wave with an amplitude of 10.5 m and period of 14.3 s is imposed. Results are shown in Figure 9. Similarly to LC3.1, platform motions and fairlead tensions are well captured by both codes. In LC3.2 wave-frequency excitation seems to be dominant even for tower base loads. The harmonics of the wave excitation in LC3.2 are further from the tower natural frequency and thus the excitation effect that can be seen in Figure 8 is less marked.

Figure 8: LC3.1. Time series of platform surge, pitch and heave degrees of freedom, tower base fore-aft force and bending moment and fairlead tensions.

To better quantify the differences between the codes, a frequency analysis of the data is shown in Figure 10. In this figure, the amplitudes and phase shifts of the wave-frequency component of the sensors in Figure 8 and Figure 9 are shown. The amplitude and phase shifts are computed by performing a Fourier transform on the previously shown data in Figure 8 and Figure 9, isolating the response at wave-frequency.

Focusing on LC3.1, both the amplitude and phase shifts of the platform’s motion are very well captured by both OF and QB, with slight over-estimation of the pitch and surge response for both codes and slight underestimation on the heave response. Similar conclusions can be drawn for the mooring line tensions, although OF is slightly closer to the experimental data in both amplitude and phase-shift. As for TB F_x and TB M_y , OF is found to greatly overestimate response at wave frequency for both load sensors. This is unexpected as OF results compare visually well to QB and experimental data. The overestimation carries over – to a lesser extent

- to LC3.2 and is likely due to the complex nature of the analysed signal. As noted for LC3.1, also in LC3.2 platform motions and fairlead 2 tension are very well captured by both codes. QB also provides good estimates of wave-frequency TB F_x and TB M_y . In conclusion, both the QB and OF models appear to be able to adequately reproduce FOWT dynamics when excited by a regular wave.

Figure 9: LC3.2. Time series of platform surge, pitch and heave degrees of freedom, tower base fore-aft force and bending moment and fairlead tensions.

Figure 10: LC3.1 Amplitude (top) and corresponding phase shift (bottom) with respect to wave elevation of wave-frequency response of key sensors

3.7. RESULTS WITH IRREGULAR WAVES AND NO WIND

Similarly to tests in regular waves, no aerodynamic loads are acting in these experiments. LC3.3 is considered to evaluate the response of the QB and OF models in these conditions. The considered wave spectrum has a significant wave height of 7.1 m and a peak spectral period of 12.1 s. As described in Table 3, a JONSWAP spectrum with a shape factor of $\gamma = 2.2$ is imposed. The response of the FOWT in irregular waves is shown in Figure 11 and Figure 12. In addition to a visual comparison, results are compared statistically and in the frequency domain.

Visual comparison of platform motions, fairlead tensions and tower base fore-aft bending moment and shear force are shown in Figure 11. Good visual agreement can be observed throughout the duration of the simulation, even after a significant simulation time. In Figure 11 the results are shown from 800 s onwards to emphasise this point, as signals are observed to remain substantially in phase. Although agreement appears to be very good, there are some observations to be made. Firstly, the numerical models generally tend to agree best with each other, with some differences that can be noted with respect to the experiments. Most significantly, if analysing the surge and pitch time series, a long-period oscillation is present in the experimental data and not present in QB and OF. Before a more quantitative comparison can be carried out in the frequency domain, it can be noted that the period of such oscillation appears to be close to the system’s natural period in the analysed degree of freedom.

Comparing statistics in Figure 12, general good agreement can be seen. A slight underestimation in peak values of wave height in QB can be seen, likely due to the approximations in the frequency-domain reconstruction of the time series. In terms of platform motions, mean values of surge are higher for OF than for QB, with the latter code being closer to experimental values. This impacts fairlead tensions, with the upwind mooring line mean loads being slightly larger for OF than QB. Heave, pitch and tower base sensors are

in good agreement in terms of mean values. Regarding fairlead tensions, as noted in Section 3.4, mean values are in very good agreement for all three time series. Greater spread can be noted between the 99% and 1% quantiles for QB in respect to OF in order to inspect extreme values. Consequently, QB appears to be more in line with experimental data in this regard. The 99% quantile for QB with respect to experiments is overestimated by 0.5% for fairlead 2 tension and by 1.5% for fairlead 1 tension. On the other hand, OF underestimates tension by approximately 1.6% and 3.3% respectively. Again, this trend is not completely unexpected as it carries over from Section 3.7, where regular wave test results were shown.

Figure 11: LC3.3 Time series of (left to right, top to bottom) wave elevation, Platform pitch, fairlead tension of downwind mooring line (line 1), platform surge, tower base fore-aft shear force, fairlead tension of upwind mooring line, platform heave, tower base fore-aft bending moment, fairlead tension of downwind mooring line (line 3).

In these tests, the fairlead load amplitude for QB was higher than for OF. Underestimation of the IQR, 99% and 1% quantiles and extreme values can be noted especially for pitch and surge for both QB and OF. This trend also carries over to tower base fore-aft force and bending moment as, especially in absence of aerodynamic loading, load cycles in these sensors are caused by inertial and gravitational effects ultimately caused by platform motion. Focusing on 99% quantiles, underestimation of TB F_x of approximately 20.8% and 16.7% for QB and OF can be noted, while TB M_y is underestimated 21.8% by QB and 6% for OF. Similar underestimations in tower base loads are noted in the results of the OC5 code-to-code comparison campaign for LPMD models, and both QB and OF are within the range of the participants' predictions [1]. The reason for such underestimation can be better explained by analysing frequency-domain results as shown in Figure 13.

Figure 12: LC3.3 Statistics. Sensor means (orange horizontal line), standard deviations (boxes), 95% quantiles (brackets) and recorded values exceeding the 95% quantile.

The PSDs of the examined load-sensors for LC3.3 are shown in Figure 13. Three distinct regions can be distinguished: low-frequencies below 0.05 Hz where the floating system natural frequencies are located, the wave excitation range between 0.05 and 0.15 Hz and the tower natural frequencies located approximately at 0.032 Hz. It is crucial to observe the amplitude of the peaks in these three regions relative to each-other; while for some load sensors such as the fairlead tensions the peaks in the low and wave frequency ranges are comparable, for platform pitch, surge and tower base sensors the low frequency peak greatly exceeds the wave-frequency excitation.

In Figure 14 and Figure 15 PSDs in low and wave frequency ranges are shown, respectively. Only a subset of the most relevant load sensors are shown for brevity. Response at wave frequency appears to be well captured by both codes as shown in Figure 15. Peak response of platform motion in the wave frequency range roughly corresponds to the peak in the wave spectra (Figure 13), while tower base fore-aft bending moment and force show two distinct peaks of response around 0.07 and 0.14 Hz. These results are in line with results from the OC5 Phase II campaign, as noted in [1]. On the other hand, as shown in Figure 14, response at the FOWTs natural frequency is not captured properly by OF or QB. As noted in [1], outside of the wave frequency range, platform motion must be excited by non-linear forces, which could be a result of second-order potential flow excitation, higher-order wave hydrodynamics or wave stretching. As noted in Section 3.1, both models include second-order potential flow excitation through QTFs. Moreover, although QB includes some additional non-linear loading sources such as Wheeler wave stretching and discrete buoyancy computation, no significant improvement in natural-frequency response prediction is noted for the present test case.

Figure 13: LC3.3 Power Spectral Density (PSD) of (left to right, top to bottom) wave elevation, platform pitch, fairlead tension of downwind mooring line (line 1), platform surge, tower base fore-aft shear force, fairlead tension of upwind mooring line, platform heave, tower base fore-aft bending moment, fairlead tension of downwind mooring line (line 3).

Figure 14: LC3.3 Power Spectral Density (PSD) of (left to right, top to bottom) platform surge, tower base fore-aft shear force, platform pitch, tower base fore-aft bending moment, fairlead tension of upwind mooring line, fairlead tension of downwind mooring line (line 3). Focus on low-frequency range (0-0.05 Hz).

Figure 15: LC3.3 Power Spectral Density (PSD) of (left to right, top to bottom) Platform surge, tower base fore-aft shear force, platform pitch, tower base fore-aft bending moment, fairlead tension of upwind mooring line, fairlead tension of downwind mooring line (line 3). Focus on wave-frequency range (0.05-0.2 Hz).

3.8. RESULTS WITH IRREGULAR WAVES AND TURBULENT WIND

During the OC5 campaign various irregular wind and wave test runs were performed. In this document, focus will be placed on LC4.1, 4.2 and 4.3. In LC4.1, the rotor is operating at its nominal design point in terms of blade pitch, TSR and wind speed. For a pitch-regulated wind turbine this corresponds to the operating point where mean aerodynamic thrust is at its peak, causing mean platform displacements to also be at their respective peaks. In LC4.2 on the other hand the turbine was tested in high winds with pitch-to-feather blades. Analysing this LC allows us to validate the numerical models in a low TSR condition. Finally, in LC4.3 the system response to a dynamic turbulent windfield close to rated wind speed is analysed. In this LC, the blades are pitched to their operating pitch angle of 1° and the rotor is held at nominal TSR. For all aforementioned LCs, irregular waves with a peak spectral period of 12.1 s and a significant wave height of 7.1 m are imposed.

In LC4.1 the wind profile has a mean of 12.91 m/s and 5% turbulence intensity. To model the drop-off in rotor speed near the bottom of the rotor, due to limitations of the experimental apparatus, wind shear is imposed in the numerical simulations using a power-law with exponent 0.2 [11]. Statistics for LC4.1 are compared in Figure 16. Both QB and OF fail to predict the mean surge position of the platform, QB underpredicting it by 7.5% and OF by 2.5%. Mean platform pitch is well predicted, with the numerical models being within 0.3° from the experiment. The tendency to underestimate tower base loads that was noted in irregular wave tests is present also in LC4.1. However, underestimation is less severe, and the improvement with respect to LC3.3 is more noticeable for QB than for OF. In fact, QB underpredicts the 99% quantile of TB F_x by 12% and of TB M_y by 9%, while OF also underpredicts the 99% quantile of TB F_x by 18 % and of TB M_y by 6%. The statistics of

aerodynamic thrust are also shown in Figure 16. Only the numerical codes are compared as aerodynamic thrust was not measured in the experiment (thrust coefficient was measured, but upon examination of the data by the authors, this measurement appears to include inertial and gravitational loads). The two codes are close in the median thrust (OF approximately 2% below QB), but OF is showing larger variations in rotor thrust, visible in the IQR and 1-99% quantiles. This aspect was not investigated further in this work package, but this is likely due to the different aerodynamic models that are being used, LLFVW in QB and DBEM in OF.

Figure 16: LC4.1 Statistics. Sensor median values (orange horizontal line), IQR (boxes), 95% quantiles (brackets) and recorded values exceeding the 95% quantile.

Figure 17: LC4.1 Power Spectral Density (PSD) of (left-right & top-bottom) wind speed tower top fore-aft shear force, aerodynamic thrust (QB and OF only), wave elevation, tower base fore-aft shear force, tower base fore-aft bending moment, platform surge and pitch, upwind fairlead tension.

As for LC3.3 analysing the signals in the frequency domain can give more insight on where the differences are located. The PSDs of a selection of relevant load sensors in LC4.1 are shown in Figure 17. Qualitatively speaking, the results appear similar to LC3.3. Here no wind excitation was present, with two distinct peaks in the wave excitation range and in the low frequency range. Focusing on tower base loads however, it can be noted that the peak in the low-frequency range is now much lower for both experiments and numerical models, and comparable to the peaks in the wave frequency range. As noted in [1], aerodynamic loading has a damping effect on platform oscillations at the system's natural frequency, reducing the discrepancies in the low-frequency range between numerical models and experiments. Moreover, as shown in Figure 17, higher-order hydrodynamic effects are not the only phenomena that may be driving low-frequency excitation, as wind excitation is present in the low-frequency range (0-0.05 Hz). These two factors explain the better agreement that is noted for the numerical models regarding extreme tower base loads. Overall, this result is again in line with what was noted in the OC5 code-to-code comparison study [1].

As for aerodynamic thrust, both codes capture several excitation peaks: at very low frequencies where wind excitation is dominant, at low frequencies where platform natural frequencies are excited and at wave frequency, where two distinct peaks arise around 0.07 Hz and 0.12 Hz. The greater variability in this metric shown by OF is noticeable as the SD signal of OF tends to be above that of QB across the entire frequency range. It must be noted that a high peak in excitation in correspondence of the 3P frequency (approximately 0.6 Hz, not shown in Figure 17) is present for both codes. The same peak is noted in the TT F_x and TB F_x sensors for the experimental data (see [11]) and appears to not be adequately captured by the numerical codes. As discussed in [11], this 3P excitation may be caused by i) non-uniformities in incoming wind – especially wind shear and ii) a slight pitch angle imbalance between the three blades. Since this WP is focused on the validation of the coupled response of QB, focus was put on low-frequency response, where wind and wave excitation is relevant. Therefore, only the former effect was introduced into QB and OF, and even this effect may be underestimated, due to uncertainties in the actual experimental wind field [11].

In LC4.3 the same wavefield is used as in LC4.1, but a dynamic wind field with a mean of 13.05 m/s and a turbulence intensity of 7.5% is imposed. The term dynamic in this case refers to a varying mean velocity of the turbulent flow over the duration of the simulation [2]. Globally the models behave very similarly to LC4.1 relative to each-other and to the experiments. Therefore, focus will be put on the differences relative to LC4.1. Statistically QB and OF appear to be reproducing well the overall behaviour of the FOWT model (Figure 18). With respect to OF, QB still slightly underestimates rotor thrust, however 99% quantiles are now very similar. The only somewhat significant difference is in the 1% quantiles that are lower for OF. In terms of frequency response (Figure 19), results look again very similar to LC4.1. Because the wind field is now dynamic, wind excitation is greatly increased with respect to LC4.1, especially at very low frequencies. The trace of such very-low frequency excitation is also visible in the tower-top and tower-base load sensors, as well as in the surge signal.

Figure 18: LC4.3 Statistics. Sensor median values (orange horizontal line), IQR (boxes), 95% quantiles (brackets) and recorded values exceeding the 95% quantile.

Figure 19: LC4.3 Power Spectral Density (PSD) of (left-right & top-bottom) wind speed tower top fore-aft shear force, aerodynamic thrust (QB and OF only), wave elevation, tower base fore-aft shear force, tower base fore-aft bending moment, platform surge and pitch, upwind fairlead tension.

In LC4.2 the turbine was tested with an equivalent full-scale wind speed of 21.09 m/s and a turbulence intensity of approximately 5%. As for LC4.1 in the numerical simulations, the vertical wind profile follows a power law with shear exponent of 0.2. Analyzing statistics in LC4.2, the same overall trends as discussed for LC4.1 can be seen. The numerical codes generally underestimate the surge motion, underestimation is similar to LC4.1 being of 7% for QB and 2% for OF. Median fairlead tension values follow from the differences observed in surge: the tension in the upwind mooring line (line 2) is underpredicted and the tension in the downwind mooring lines is overpredicted. Focusing on tower base extreme loads, the 99% quantiles are in even better agreement with the experiments in this operating condition,

although some underprediction remains. TB M_y is underpredicted by 4% and 1% by QB and OF respectively and TB F_x is underpredicted by 14% and 10% respectively. Once again, the causes for the observed differences can be seen in Figure 21, where PSDs are shown. In this above-rated operating condition, the peak in correspondence of the system pitch natural frequency in the tower base loads is now smaller than the peaks in the wave-excitation region. The numerical models continue to fail to properly predict excitation in this region, but since this loading source is less significant in these conditions, and both QB and OF are much closer to the experiments, 99% quantiles are in better agreement. Physically speaking this is again due to the combined action of wind excitation and aerodynamic damping. In respect to LC4.1, wind excitation seems to be more relevant, not as relevant as in LC4.3 however. Very low frequency ($f < 0.05$ Hz) excitation appears in the PSDs of TB F_x and TT F_x for QB and OF (Figure 21), but not for the experiments, which is unexpected. Overall, system dynamics are very well captured in above-rated conditions, and QB can be considered validated on the present test case in these conditions.

Figure 20: LC4.2 Statistics. Sensor median values (orange horizontal line), IQR (boxes), 95% quantiles (brackets) and recorded values exceeding the 95% quantile.

3.9. SUMMARY

The 5MW OC5 FOWT model, a 1:50 scale model wind turbine mounted on a semi-submersible type platform, was investigated. A range of test cases from the experimental campaign were chosen for comparisons as a verification platform between OF and QB and as a validation platform for the QB software developed in WP1 and WP2. Both first- and second-order hydrodynamic loads have been accounted for in the models. Decay tests were first simulated to demonstrate that natural frequencies and damping behaviour was correctly captured by the models. Very good agreement was noted between the numerical models and experiments in these tests. Following this, tests in regular wave fields were carried out. Overall, system response in amplitude as in phase shift with respect to the incoming waves was very good for

both OF and QB in terms of motions and fairlead tensions. The mean values also appear to be captured very well by both numerical codes. In these tests, better agreement with experiments was noted when wave time series from the basin tests are used as input to the numerical models. A spectral analysis of the signal revealed the presence of higher-order harmonics, exciting system frequencies other than the wave frequency.

Figure 21: LC4.2 Power Spectral Density (PSD) of (left to right and top to bottom) wind speed tower top fore-aft shear force, aerodynamic thrust (QB and OF only), wave elevation, tower base fore-aft shear force, tower base fore-aft bending moment, platform surge and pitch, upwind fairlead tension

A number of irregular wave tests were then carried out in order to inspect frequency content of the turbine response. From a visual comparison, the response of the various load sensors are well in-phase even several minutes into the test-runs. A statistical analysis revealed an underprediction of low-frequency platform response caused by the excitement of the system’s natural frequencies. This also led to underestimations in the 99% quantiles of tower base fore-aft shear force and bending moments of about 25-20%. As noted in [1] this is due to higher-order wave hydrodynamic effects, for which including second-order excitation is not sufficient. The QB response was generally well verified against OF, placing it furthermore in alignment with the performance of the other codes used for comparison in the OC5 campaign.

Finally, a range of fully coupled tests were carried out where aerodynamic loads were acting on the rotor. In these cases, QB was able to capture excitation due to the turbulent wind field at rated and above rated wind conditions very well. Tower base loads were found to be underpredicted. This was concluded to again be caused by higher-order hydrodynamic effects. The deviation from experimental results were however shown to be relatively small- of the order between 4% and 15% depending on the specific error metric and wind/wave condition. Overall QB performed as well as or better than the state-of-the-art code OF in these simulations.

3.10. CHAPTER REFERENCES

- [1] Robertson, A., Wendt, F., Jonkman, J., Popko, W., Dagher, H., Gueydon, S., Qvist, J., Vittori, F., Azcona, J., Uzunoglu, E., et al., OC5 Project Phase II: Validation of Global Loads of the DeepCwind Floating Semisubmersible, *Wind TurbineEnergy Procedia* 137 (2017) 38–57.
- [2] Robertson A., Jonkman, J., Wendt, F., Goupee, A. and Dagher, H., Definition of the OC5 DeepCwind Semisubmersible Floating System, National Renewable Energy Lab, University of Maine.
- [3] Perez-Becker, S., Behrens de Luna, R., Aero-Hydro-Elastic Model Definition in QBlade Ocean, Technical Report: Deliverable 2.1, FLOATECH Project, H2020-EU.3.3.2. – Low-cost, low-carbon energy supply EU project, 2022.
- [4] Snel, H. and Schepers, J., Joint investigation of dynamic inflow effects and implementation of an engineering method, Netherlands, 1995.
- [5] Damiani, R. and Greg, H., The Dynamic Stall Module for FAST 8, 2016.
- [6] Goupee, A., Kimball, R. de Ridder, E.-J., Helder, J., Robertson, A., Jonkman, J., A Calibrated Blade Element/Momentum Theory Aerodynamic Model of the MARIN Stock Wind Turbine, International Society of Offshore and Polar Engineers Conference (ISOPE 2015), Kona, Hawaii, 2015.
- [7] WAMIT User Manual Version 7.4, WAMIT Inc., Chestnut Hill, MA 02467-2504, USA, <https://www.wamit.com/>
- [8] QBlade Documentation Page, <https://docs.qblade.org/>, online, last access 11.08.2022.
- [9] Perez-Becker, S., Papi, F., Saverin, J., Marten, D., Bianchini, A., Paschereit, C. O., Is the Blade Element Momentum Theory Overestimating Wind Turbine Loads? – An Aeroelastic Comparison Between OpenFAST’s AeroDyn and QBlade’s Lifting-Line Free Vortex Wake Method, *Wind Energy Science* 5, 721-743, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.5194/wes-5-721-2020>.
- [10] Behrens de Luna, R., et al., Comparison of different fidelity aerodynamic solvers on the IEA 10 MW turbine including novel tip extension geometries, *J. Phys.: Conf. Ser.* 2265 032002, 2022.
- [11] Wendt, F., Andersen, M., Robertson, A., Jonkman, J., Verification and Validation of the New Dynamic Mooring Modules Available in FAST v8, 2016.

4. VALIDATION RESULTS FOR THE SOFTWIND 10 MW FLOATING WIND TURBINE

In this section the SOFTWIND experiments carried out at the Research Laboratory in Hydrodynamics, Energetics and Atmospheric Environment (LHEEA) department of the Ecole Centrale de Nantes will be described. As was done for the OC5 experiment in the previous section, this experimental database has been used as a validation platform for the three software packages compared in Task 2.1 of the FLOATECH project: QB, OF and DLW. In addition, important features regarding the numerical models are described. The simulations with DLW additionally provide a reference validation case prior to the numerical verification presented in Section 5.

Figure 22: SOFTWIND model visualization in QB (left). The unrelaxed mooring line configuration is shown whereby the load cells are initially aligned vertically. SOFTWIND experimental platform in the wave tank of LHEEA (right).

4.1. DESCRIPTION OF THE EXPERIMENT

The SOFTWIND experiments were designed to simulate the behaviour of a 10MW floating wind turbine at 1:40 scale [1]. The experiments allowed the demonstration and validation of a software-in-the-loop (SIL) system whereby a closed-loop control system was employed to emulate the thrust force acting on the full-scale turbine model in real time. The conceptual design of the experimental scale turbine was based heavily on the DTU 10MW Reference Wind Turbine [2], hereafter DTU10MW. The experiments were carried out between November 2019 and March 2020 in the Hydrodynamic and Ocean Engineering wave tank of the LHEEA of Ecole Centrale de Nantes. The experiments were conducted in two campaigns. In the first campaign, carried out between Dec. 2019 and Jan. 2020, system eigenvalues and characteristics were investigated without aerodynamic loads in order to allow for validation of the model properties and future tuning of the numerical models. This included a range of decay tests, regular wave tests and irregular wave tests. In campaign two, carried out from Feb.-Mar. 2020, the SIL system was activated and the fully coupled aero-hydro-servo-elastic system was

simulated for both regular and irregular sea states. The experimental turbine consists of a flexible tower mounted on a spar-buoy type platform. The mooring system consisted of three catenary lines. These were connected by delta connections to the fairleads directly below the spar taper. The mooring line delta connections were used in order to provide yawing stiffness as seen in Figure 22 and are numbered as seen in Figure 24. A load cell was used to connect each mooring line delta connection point which allows for the collection of mooring line tensions during the experimental runs. A ducted electric fan mounted on the tower top was actuated to generate the equivalent aerodynamic thrust force, which was calculated by OF in real time based on the measured motion and specified windfield (see details below). A range of sensors were used to collect experimental data during both campaigns. These sensors are summarised in Table 5.

Table 5: Sensor data collected during the SOFTWIND experiments.

Sensor Name	Description	Coordinate system (CS)
CoG_motion	Translational degrees of freedom of the floater centre of gravity	Global CS
CoG_rotation	Rotational degrees of freedom of the floater centre of gravity	Global CS
Mooring tension	Mooring line 1-3 tensions at the position of the delta connection	Local: X component of mooring line CS
Tower base bending moment	Bending moment at the tower base	Local: Y component of tower base CS
Aerodynamic thrust	Aerodynamic thrust force at hub	Local: X component of Hub CS
Wave elevation	Wave heights (numerous positions).	Local: Z component of local CS (water surface)

For the SIL experiments, a digital twin of the experimental rotor was generated within OF. The hydrodynamic loads were directly produced at model scale by wave-tank experiments. The servo-aerodynamic loading were synchronously calculated at full scale and represented at model scale by means of the aerodynamic actuator. In this way, the dynamics of the full-scale

floater could be reproduced. The blade aerodynamic definition, blade structural properties and rotor nacelle assembly (RNA) description were taken from this definition. As elastic scaling of the tower was unfeasible, a tower redesign was carried out with two objectives in mind: To capture an acceptable frequency range for the first fore-aft and side-side tower modes and to have a comparable integrated stiffness with regards to the amplitude of deformations. By accounting for the turbine 1P and 3P frequencies and the wave field excitations, an iterative procedure was employed to generate a suitable experimental tower [1].

The wind turbine controller is based on the DTU Baseline Controller for the DTU10MW. The parameters are largely as specified for the reference turbine, however with a modified gain scheduled proportional integral controller. The values modified here were the proportional and integral gains of the pitch controller and the linear and quadratic aerodynamic gain scheduling coefficients. This was done to avoid issues with negative damping during platform pitching motions. The controller PI parameters optimized for the public definition of the Olaf Olsen (OO-Star) 10MW FWT [3] have been used as the pitch natural frequencies between the two models coincide.

Figure 23: Full-scale SOFTWIND model (left). Laboratory-scale SOFTWIND model with aerodynamic actuator (right).

The floater was designed in such a way as to achieve a representative behaviour of a 10MW floating wind turbine at the given scale. The definition was based heavily on the OC3 Hywind SPAR platform [4]. Static design parameters included the metacentric height GM and trim angle at rated rotor thrust. Frequency design parameters included the natural periods in roll, heave and pitch and platform motion response amplitude operators (RAOs) [1]. For the conversion of the experimental results to the SIL model within OF, a Froude scaling was carried

out [5]. The experimental data which has been collected has also been Froude scaled in order to allow comparison with the simulated full-scale models. This allowed expression of experimental time, displacements and forces at full-scale. Reynolds number scaling for the aerodynamics is automatically accounted for with the use of the SIL aerodynamic model.

4.2. DESCRIPTION OF THE NUMERICAL MODELS

The SOFTWIND experiment has been replicated in three software packages for the purposes of validation prior to the further tasks in WP2 of the FLOATECH project. These models are briefly described here along with an overview of key differences in the models. The turbine definition, taken from the OF definition applied in the SIL experiments and described in [1], provided the basis for all models. For brevity, only deviations from this definition which were applied in the simulations are described in the following sections. In all simulations the tower and blades are treated as being flexible and the platform is treated as being rigid. In addition, the controller has been taken from the SIL definition. For all simulations hydrodynamic loads have been calculated using a potential flow model to calculate radiation forces and diffraction loads from waves. Drag forces on submerged elements are calculated using a Morison approach along with a quadratic damping matrix which acts at the platform reference point. It was found during simulations that the coupled system displayed great sensitivity to the mooring system parameters. For this reason, it was decided among the participants that fixing the mooring line anchoring positions, while allowing free choice of mooring line unstretched length provided a necessary degree of modelling freedom. All models make use of a sea-bed spring approach to model the mooring line resting on the sea bed.

The QB model of the SOFTWIND 10MW is publicly available at the following location:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6397358>

This model is described in the Deliverable D2.1 of the FLOATECH project [6]. There are some modifications which were made to the model described in this deliverable. The blade aerodynamic definition has been modified in order to align with the definition used in the SIL experiments. Two aerodynamic models are available within QB for time-resolved simulations: the unsteady BEM model (UBEM) [7] and the lifting line free vortex wake model [8]. For the unsteady simulations carried out in the work here, the LLFVW model has been applied as it allows for a higher fidelity treatment of unsteady rotor loads and wake aerodynamics than the UBEM model [9]. The ϕ_{ye} dynamic stall model has been activated to account for unsteady aerodynamic effect on the blades [10]. The platform buoyancy was modelled using an explicit buoyancy approach whereby the substructure is discretized into cylindrical sections and buoyancy forces are discretely applied. In order to improve the platform static pitch position, the centre of gravity (COG) of the substructure was shifted slightly forwards to $x=-0.05\text{m}$. An additional quadratic damping in pitch and roll DOFs with magnitude $1.0\text{e}+10 \text{ (Nm)/}(\text{rad/s})^2$ were applied at the platform reference point in order to improve the agreement of the damping of the system with the corresponding decay experiments. In order to improve the

mooring line tensions and natural frequency in the decay tests, the mooring line lengths were specified as $L_1 = 632\text{m}$, $L_2 = 630.8\text{ m}$ and $L_3 = 631.2\text{m}$.

In OF the structural model is treated with the module ElastoDyn [11]. Deflections of the turbine blades and tower are calculated as a superposition of pre-calculated deflection modes. In order to align with the aerodynamic model applied in the SIL experiments, AeroDyn 14 has been used to calculate aerodynamic loads and the corresponding model definition has been taken from the SOFTWIND database. A Beddoes-Leishman dynamic stall model is applied to account for unsteady aerodynamic effects [12]. The buoyancy forces are calculated as the sum of a constant force applied at the centre of buoyancy along with a linear stiffness matrix to account for the deviatoric term due to changes of the waterplane area. The mooring lines are treated as flexible cable elements with a catenary model. As with QB, an additional quadratic damping factor has been added with a magnitude of $8.0\text{e}+09\text{ (Nm)/(rad/s)}^2$ in the roll and pitch DOFs to improve the agreement with the decay tests. In addition, a linear damping term of magnitude $3.0\text{e}+04\text{ N/(m/s)}$ was added in the surge DOF. In order to improve the mooring line tensions and natural frequency in the decay tests, the mooring line lengths were specified as $L_1 = 637\text{ m}$, $L_2 = 637\text{ m}$ and $L_3 = 637.2\text{m}$.

Within DLW, the aerodynamic definition has again been based on aerodynamic definition from the SIL experiments. In this case no unsteady blade aerodynamics model has been applied. Some small modifications were made to the mooring line hydrodynamic coefficients in order to improve response in the decay tests. As with the other models, a quadratic damping has been applied to the entire floater system of magnitude $1.0\text{e}+10\text{ (Nm)/(rad/s)}^2$. In order to improve the mooring line tensions and natural frequency in the decay tests, the mooring line lengths were slightly modified to $L_1 = 632.3\text{ m}$, $L_2 = 631.1\text{ m}$, $L_3 = 631.5\text{ m}$.

A number of important points should be raised regarding modelling differences between the software packages. These are described sequentially below:

Structural modelling: The modelling approaches used in OF are less amenable to large, nonlinear deflections as compared to the models in QB and DL. Within the SOFTWIND experiments however only moderate deflections have been observed.

Aerodynamic modelling: The BEM aerodynamic models of OF and DLW are based on the assumption of a converged wake state. The LLFVW of QB however discretely treats changes in rotor induction due to unsteady circulation changes over the blade. In steady cases these two models agree, however in unsteady cases the instantaneous aerodynamic loads observed by the turbine will deviate [9]. These loads directly influence the deflections and motion of the turbine and floater system. The aerodynamic model of AeroDyn v14 used in the SIL experiments furthermore does not account for rotor coning or blade pre-bend.

Hydrodynamic modelling: Within OF, the buoyancy force is modelled as a constant vertical force acting at the centre of buoyancy of the platform. Deviations in buoyancy are calculated with a linear stiffness matrix. Within QB and DLW, explicit buoyancy has been applied to

calculate the buoyancy of the body. This method calculates the buoyancy of discrete segments based on the position and orientation of the displaced fluid. A distributed buoyancy load is applied at each cylindrical section. In order to avoid incorrectly accounting for changes in buoyancy due to wave crests and troughs, the static buoyancy flag has been activated in QB to ensure that only the mean water level is used to calculate buoyancy forces [10].

Mooring Line modelling: Mooring line elements are treated in QB as cables with the cable Absolute Nodal Coordinate Formulation (ANCF) elements of project Chrono [13]. These allow for large elastic deformations as opposed to classical cable element catenary treatments as applied in OF and DLW. In addition to this, the equivalent spring system which is used to model the mooring line resting on the sea bed has a different spring stiffness in the three models. Although this will likely have a small effect on the platform equilibrium position, this may influence dynamic loads on the mooring lines. In all three models, the load cell connection between mooring lines and delta connection is treated as a rigid element with the upscaled experimental weight and length.

Simulation Setup: The general setup of a system between the three models differs greatly in terms of the user options available. As an example, QB and OF allow for an initially relaxed structural solution to be found prior to the simulation with full hydrodynamic / aerodynamic loads. This relaxed solution can be specified with an arbitrary combination of initial turbine conditions. This feature is not available in DLW, necessitating the removal of an initial transient settling period for unsteady simulations. In addition to this, when using DLW with a controller, the aerodynamic thrust acts only after a given settling period. This may give rise naturally to very strong initial transient responses from the floater. All numerical models were set up so that the output sensors match the measured sensors in the experiment, shown in Table 5.

4.3. DESCRIPTION OF THE LOAD CASES

A multitude of decay, regular wave and irregular wave experiments were carried out in the SOFTWIND experiments. As the purpose of this investigation is to validate QB against the experimental data and the established codes, validating against all of these cases would be highly redundant. For this reason, a compact range of experimental cases have been chosen to highlight the functionality, similarities and differences in the solvers. These cases are summarised in Table 6 and can be observed to align well with the cases carried out for the OC5 test cases in Section 3.

For all tests cases in campaign 1, the SIL was not activated and therefore the turbine system was not affected by any aerodynamic loads. At the completion of this campaign, the mooring system was disassembled and the buoy removed from the wave tank. In campaign 2 the entire system was reassembled for the tests involving the SIL system, here load cases LC2.3 and LC3.2. For the SIL campaigns the aerodynamic actuator was mounted on the tower top. The

reassembly, which resulted in changes in mass distribution and resting equilibrium positions, will play a role in the discussion regarding the SIL cases in the following sections.

Table 6: Load cases for the SOFTWIND model validation.

Load Case Nr.	Campaign	Description	Wind Condition	Wave Condition
LC1.1	1	Surge Decay	None	None
LC1.2	1	Heave Decay	None	None
LC1.3	1	Pitch Decay	None	None
LC2.1	1	Reg. Wave 1 No Wind	None	H = 9 m, T = 18 s
LC2.2	1	Reg. Wave 2: No Wind	None	H = 7.5 m, T = 12 s
LC2.3	2	Reg. Wave 3: Wind	Uniform 11.4 m/s	H = 7.4 m, T = 12.4 s
LC3.1	1	Irreg. Wave 1: No Wind	None	Bretschneider Hs = 9 m, Tp = 18 s
LC3.2	2	Irreg. Wave 2: Wind	18 m/s TI = 17%; turbulent	Bretschneider Hs = 5.8 m, Tp = 10.9 s

For all cases investigated, the wind and waves are incident from the wave heading 0 degrees. Combined with the (approximately) symmetrical distribution of the mooring system and SOFTWIND floater geometry implies that that surge, heave and pitch DOFs will predominantly be affected in the load cases. For this reason, these decay cases were chosen to examine the natural frequencies, linear and quadratic damping effects of the floater under unforced conditions. The decay tests additionally allow for validation of the dynamical coupling between DOFs in the models.

Following the decay tests, the regular wave tests are investigated. In these cases, a regular wave was generated at one side of the wave basin by a wavemaker according to a specified driving signal. The experimental wave height data was collected from an array of resistive wave probes in the basin. The layout and numbering of these probes changed between campaigns as illustrated in Figure 24. For the simulations carried out in the investigations, the time-resolved wave data from these wave probes was used to generate synthetic wave fields

by carrying out a Fourier decomposition. Due to the nature of the wave field and the testing basin, it has been assessed that the wave height data at the lateral positions of the sensors are representative of the wave height at the floater position. Care must be taken to ensure the correct sensor data has been used for generation of the synthetic wave field. For the SIL cases (campaign 2), the WG1 sensor data was utilized while for all other cases (campaign 1) the WG2 sensor was used.

Figure 24: Mooring line and wave gauge configuration of the SOFTWIND experiment. Campaign 1: System characterization (left). Campaign 2: SIL experiments (right).

In the experimental cases where the SIL system was activated (LC2.3 and LC3.2), prior to the initialization of the wavemaker, the wind field was ramped up linearly over 40 s (250 s at full scale) in order to ensure that the turbine system was able to reach an equilibrium state prior to exposure to the wave field. This gives rise to an altered initial position of the system, which must be accounted for in the simulations in order to avoid large transients occurring in the initial phase of the simulation. Load cases 3.1 and 3.2 consider a wave field with irregular waves. As with the regular wave cases, the wave height data at the turbine position was collected with a range of wave gauges. For the two unsteady wave cases investigated, both the time domain signal along with the PSD of the wave fields were compared to the experimental series to ensure that the virtual wave field was representative of the experimental field.

4.4. RESULTS OF THE DECAY TEST

Before a detailed discussion of the individual decay tests, an overview is given of the natural frequencies obtained from the numerical models and the experiments in each DOF investigated. These values were calculated by performing a spectral analysis of the

corresponding DOF time series and extracting the dominant frequency from the signal. The values have been normalised with the collected experimental value and are shown in Figure 25.

Figure 25: Normalised simulated natural frequencies of the SOFTWIND platform.

It can be observed that, in general, all codes have approximately reproduced the natural frequencies of the coupled system, with deviations generally on the order of a few percent. Some deviations are observed, particularly the heave DOF for the DLW model. It was generally found that a compromise must be struck up between matching heave equilibrium position and surge and heave natural frequencies. A brief description of the decay tests is given here before the proceeding discussion. For each DOF the decay test was executed by initially displacing the floater in the given DOF, allowing the system to settle and then releasing the floater such that it dynamically oscillates back to the equilibrium position of the floater. It was observed that the equilibrium position of each DOF due to the influence of gravity, mass distribution and mooring lines forces is slightly offset from the equilibrium reference position. This is important for the ensuing discussions on the forcing cases as the simulated mooring line tensions showed a strong dependency on the equilibrium positions.

The times series for the surge decay test are shown in Figure 26. It can generally be seen that the agreement is good for all three codes. The slightly lower natural frequency of the OF model is seen to compound over the duration of the oscillation, this aligns with the lower relative natural frequency seen in Figure 25. In Figure 26, a large coupling between the surge and pitch DOFs can be seen. It is observed that the OF and DLW static heave are slightly above the experiment value. The slightly higher equilibrium position of the floater in the OF simulations will be consistently observed in all test cases. This is most likely due to the use of a difference in buoyancy models between OF and QB/DLW. The linear stiffness matrix was calculated using the software package NEMOH [14], which incorporates the mass properties of the platform. Small deviations in the platform or turbine mass or volume then naturally give rise to a deviation in the floater equilibrium position. This requires then iterative tuning of the linear stiffness matrix, which is generally neglected due to the small impact on results of slight deviations in the heave resting position.

For brevity, in the following discussion TX shall be used as shorthand for the tension in mooring line X. T1 therefore refers to the mooring line tension in the mooring line which runs *downwind* of the turbine. For motions of low yaw, it can be expected that T2 and T3 agree due

the symmetry of the mooring configurations. Inspecting the mooring line tensions, it can be seen that QB and OF generally tend to predict higher mooring line tensions than the experiment. DLW predicts T1 closer to the experimental value while underpredicting T2 and T3. Curiously, it is also observed that the static value of T3 is slightly below that of T2. This may be explained by the slightly non-symmetric positions of the anchoring points M2 and M3 (Figure 24). This was reflected in the OF definition used in the experimental campaign for the SIL tests and an attempt was made by all participants to account for that by having different anchoring positions and slightly different mooring line lengths.

Figure 26: Surge decay test of the SOFTWIND platform.

The equilibrium surge position of the floater appears to be well captured by all models. This was achieved by finding suitable mooring line lengths which produce i) the correct equilibrium surge positions, ii) accurate mooring line tensions and iii) surge natural frequencies. As mentioned previously, the coupled system demonstrated great sensitivity to changes in mooring line length with regards to the aforementioned values. This, combined with the difference in modelling approaches for the mooring lines help explain why a disparity is seen in the chosen mooring line lengths between models.

The results for the heave decay tests are shown in Figure 27. It is observed that QB produces the best agreement with the heave DOF. As seen previously, OF slightly overpredicts the heave static position and a very slight positive phase shift is observed as compared to experiment. In this case, the static surge position of the QB simulation appears to be slightly lower than the value in the experiments. This is not visible in the surge decay test due to the scale of the surge

motion. A trend here is observed when inspecting the mooring line tensions that QB and OF appear to overpredict T1 and T3, while better agreement is found with T2. The T1 agreement for DLW is again found to be accurate. This trend generally persists for most of the following test cases.

Figure 27: Heave decay test of the SOFTWIND platform.

The results for the pitch decay tests are shown in Figure 28. Here the models again reproduce well the behaviour seen in the experiment. The strong surge-pitch coupling is clearly observed. The slight overprediction of the surge natural frequency in OF is seen to influence the pitch DoF signal. The time series appear to agree well with the experiment, with the exception of OF where, towards the end of the situation, the difference in surge natural frequency gives rise to a phase shift. As with the other decay tests, it can be observed that OF and DLW both overpredict the submergence depth while this is nearly matched in QB.

To better understand the differences in the mooring line tensions seen in the decay tests, it is instructive here to investigate possible explanations for these deviations. Table 7 shows a summary of experimental uncertainties for mooring line parameters, taken from the SOFTWIND experiment definition [1]. In order to investigate the influence these experimental parameters have on the mooring line tensions, in QB a trial simulation was carried out whereby the mooring line and load cell masses were reduced by the value specified in Table 7 and the mooring line lengths were shortened to match the experimental values. The system was allowed to decay freely to the modified static equilibrium position. It was found that the equilibrium mooring line tensions [T1, T2, T3] were increased by approximately [0.3, 0.2, 0.2]

MN due to line shortening, which is close to the discrepancies seen between the codes and the experimental mooring line tensions. At these specified lengths, significant discrepancies could be observed in the equilibrium position of the floater with respect to the experiment. In addition to this test, a thorough analysis was carried out on the experimental data for both campaigns and three families of tests were found with static T3 values between 2.43 MN and 2.5 MN.

Figure 28: Pitch decay test of the SOFTWIND platform.

Table 7: SOFTWIND mooring line experimental uncertainties.

Value	Measured value	Uncertainty
Mooring line 1 chain length [m]	627.6	0.4
Mooring line 2 chain length [m]	629.6	0.4
Mooring line 3 chain length [m]	628.8	0.4
Mass of mooring chain [kg/m]	379	1.6
Mass of load cell [kg]	27,500	1,280

The trial simulation carried out in QB including the experimental mooring line parameter uncertainties, along with the experimental differences observed in the mooring line tension illustrate clearly the sensitivity of mooring line tensions in the experiment to both mass parameters and also mooring line lengths. This also provides an explanation for the aforementioned point regarding the compromise between mooring line tensions and platform positions. It is therefore concluded that the deviation of the numerical models to the experimental tensions observed in the decay tests are acceptable. It will be observed in the following tests that comparable deviations were in general seen for all test cases investigated here.

4.5. RESULTS OF THE AERODYNAMIC COMPARISONS

In the experimental decay tests, aerodynamic loads were not applied as the SIL system was not activated. For the proceeding comparison cases LC2.3 and LC3.2 however, aerodynamic loads will act on the turbine system. The integrated force of the aerodynamic loads on the turbine blades as calculated in the SIL model were applied to the experimental rotor in the form of a single thrust force applied in the x-direction of the tower top coordinate system through the use of an aerodynamic actuator. In order to ensure that the simulated results align with those of the experiment, it is crucial to reproduce as closely as possible the aerodynamic definition used in the SIL experiments. This model is based on the model of the DTU10MW described in [14] and uses the aerodynamic model of AeroDyn14. The number of blade stations was reduced to allow real-time SIL calculations. By nature of the AeroDyn14 model, the rotor coning angle is not accounted for. As each software package makes use of a different aerodynamic model, a comparison has been carried out here to investigate the behaviour of each aerodynamic model to assist in the discussions in the proceeding sections.

Each software package has a predefined set of allowable outputs for each aerodynamic module. Leaving the turbine definitions unmodified hence would require tedious post-processing in order to ensure that all output values indeed corresponded to purely aerodynamics loads in the desired coordinate systems. For this reason, a simplified turbine definition was adopted for the purposes of the aerodynamic comparison. This model has a rigid tower, no shaft tilt and no coning angle. This removes mass and inertial loads which act on the rotor shaft. The aerodynamic model within AeroDyn14 specifies panel-centre properties. This therefore requires an interpolated aerodynamic blade definition from that provided for the DTU10MW. The turbine blades were pre-bent as defined for the DTU10MW, and were allowed to elastically deflect.

As the aerodynamic loads in the coupled SIL system were applied purely in the form of a single thrust force acting on the rotor shaft, this value has been inspected for each of the turbine definitions and the turbine power has been ignored. Two operating regimes were selected for the aerodynamic comparison. These configurations were chosen to represent

aerodynamically operating points in both below and above rated control regimes. In both cases, the inflow velocity and pitch angle were set constant and the rotor speed was varied. For each operating point, the aerodynamics were allowed to converge (in the case of an unsteady BEM or LLFVW calculation) and the converged values were taken. The two cases investigated have been summarised in Table 8.

Table 8: Cases used for the SOFTWIND aerodynamic comparison

Variables	Below Rated	Above Rated
Wind speed [m/s]	8	15
Collective pitch angle [deg]	0	15
Rotational speed [rpm]	3, 3.5, 4.0, ..., 15	2.5, 3.0, ..., 9

It should be noted that at rated conditions of wind speed 11 m/s and turbine rotation rate of 9.6 RPM, the turbine reaches a TSR of 8.15. At higher wind speeds during actual operation, the rotation rate is held constant while the turbine pitches out, resulting in progressively lower TSR values for increasing wind speeds. The collective pitch value of 15° for the above rated condition correspond approximately to the case of wind speed 18.5 m/s, or a TSR of 4.8.

Figure 29: Thrust values for the SOFTWIND models. Left: Below rated conditions (wind speed 8 m/s, collective pitch angle 0°). Right: above rated conditions (wind speed 15 m/s, collective pitch angle 15°).

The integrated thrust force of the rotor for both operating points is shown in Figure 29. For completeness, the results of the QB UBEM model are also included as this provides insights into differences between BEM and LLFVW style aerodynamics approaches, which both use exactly the same blade aerodynamic definition. In the below rated condition it is seen that up to TSR 8 all models agree quite well with the exception of DLW, which appears to deviate by approximately 5% as compared to the other codes. It is seen that the QB UBEM and QB LLFVW

slightly disagree by approximately 3% between TSR 4.5 and 6. AeroDyn14 and AeroDyn15 agree quite well. Beyond TSR 8, the model predictions start to diverge. It is important to note that for the TSRs relevant for normal turbine operation, the LLFVW model and AeroDyn14 models used in QB and OF respectively agree quite well. At TSR 12 however, the DLW thrust appears to disagree with the other models by approximately 15%. These results demonstrate that the thrust results should be comparable under unsteady conditions for the rated case LC2.3.

Inspecting now the model for the above rated case, much larger deviations between the models are observed. It is again seen that for lower TSR, the codes generally agree however for increasing TSR (corresponding to decreasing wind speed) the agreement between the models becomes much stronger. In general, AeroDyn15, QB UBEM and QB LLFVW agree well until TSR 4 while AeroDyn14 predicts a much larger thrust force. The thrust of the DLW model appears again to be below the other models. The variation in loads here may influence the above rated case LC3.2 which corresponds approximately to the case of TSR 5 in the figure above. Here it is seen that the thrust deviation from AeroDyn14 is approximately -8% for QB and -13% for DLW.

These results correspond only to the behaviour of the aerodynamic models under steady aerodynamic conditions. Under the action of a wave field, the turbine platform will translate and rotate, inducing motion in the rotor plane. The introduction of unsteady aerodynamic effects may give rise to larger discrepancies between the models. This will be discussed in the proceeding validation cases.

4.6. RESULTS WITH REGULAR WAVES AND CONSTANT WIND

The predictions made by all tools will now be compared for the case where the platform is exposed to a regular wave field. As aerodynamic loads are not acting in these experiments, only platform motions and mooring line tensions will be analysed. The regular wave experiments had a (scaled) duration of approximately 400 s, however to avoid issues with the time series due to the periodicity of the Fourier synthesis around 400 s, results are displayed here only for the initial 300 s of each experiment.

The results for LC2.1 are shown in Figure 30. In this case, the wave field initially ramps up slowly and converges to a wave field with wave height of 9 m and period of 18 s. An analytical analysis of the heave response amplitude operator (RAO) for the spar buoy demonstrates that below the critical wave period of 30 s, the floater heave response should be in phase with the exciting wave. This result is indeed observed in all models and the experiment. The same can be said of the other DOFs. In all models, it can be seen that an additional transient is present in the surge. This appears to be stronger in the QB and DLW results than the OF results. This is possibly a result of a slightly erroneous initial condition of the floater. The specification of an initial position is not possible in DLW, however this result may be slightly improved in QB through trial and error. Here it is again seen, as with the decay tests, that the equilibrium

heave position of OF is above the other models. The amplitude of the pitch response of all models is slightly underpredicted by all models.

It can be seen that the amplitude of oscillation of T1 is much larger in the experiments than in the simulations. This is somewhat counterintuitive as the motion is generally well captured by all models. It is seen that T1 aligns quite well between QB and OF, and as was observed in the decay tests the equilibrium value lies above that of DLW. More investigation is required to explain the small amplitude of the T1 compared to the models. As would be expected intuitively due to the layout of the mooring lines, a smaller amplitude for T2 and T3 is observed than T1 as the tension arising due to motion in surge direction is shared over L2 and L3. The now familiar trend is observed that QB and OF agree well while the DLW model predicts a lower tension.

Figure 30: Comparison with SOFTWIND experiment for case LC2.1: wave height $H = 9\text{ m}$ and wave period $T = 18\text{ s}$.

In order to provide a comparative basis for LC2.3 without aerodynamic loads, a second unforced regular wave case was investigated with a wave height of 7.5 m and a period of 12 s. The results are shown in Figure 31. Compared to the previous test case LC2.1, this case has a lower wave height and an increased frequency. Similar trends can be seen as with LC2.1. The transient in this case is larger, most likely due to the increased frequency of the wave series. The results coincide well with those of the previous case, however the amplitudes of motion are seen to be decreased, as is expected for the lower significant wave height. These influence directly the mooring line tensions of the system. It can be seen that in this case the

line tensions of T1 is overpredicted by all models and QB and OF slightly overpredict T2 and T3.

Figure 31: Comparison with SOFTWIND experiment for case LC2.2: wave height $H = 7.5$ m and wave period $T = 12$ s

The final load case LC2.3 includes the effects of aerodynamic loading. This is a significantly more challenging case for a number of reasons. As described in the aerodynamic comparison, the motion of the floater is highly dependent on the correct specification of the unsteady thrust loads on the rotor. It was observed in the aerodynamic comparison that there are indeed differences in the steady thrust loads. It is likely that even larger discrepancies in the unsteady aerodynamic loads will be observed due to model behaviour in unsteady regimes. The second point is that the model now includes the controller which was applied in the SIL experiments. Unlike the previous cases, there is now active thrust and rotor speed modulation depending on the platform motion and wind field. The SIL experiments were initialized by ramping up the wind speed over 50 s to the inflow wind speed shown (11.4 m/s). This allowed the floater to reach an equilibrium position, which necessarily differs greatly from the unforced cases due to the additional thrust load and redistributed mooring line tensions. Following this initial ramp-up period, the wave generator was activated and the regular wave field was progressively ramped up over approximately 150 s.

Figure 32 shows the time series for LC2.3. In order to simplify the comparison, only the time from 100 s to 300 s is considered to avoid strong effects caused by initial transients. For QB and OF cases an initial simulation was carried out without the wave field in order to specify the static equilibrium position including aerodynamic thrust. This equilibrium position was

then used as the initial displacement of the system. A period of dynamic relaxation was simulated prior to the initialization of the wind field to allow the mooring line system to reach an equilibrium configuration prior to the onset of aerodynamic loads at the beginning of the simulation. This functionality is not included in DLW, giving rise to strong transients in the DLW simulations. In addition to this point, when a turbine controller is specified within DLW, the simulation proceeds initially without aerodynamic loads acting for 50 s in order to allow the controller response to stabilize. Following this, the aerodynamic thrust loads act instantaneously after this time. This naturally gives rise to a very strong initial transient in the simulation and will be discussed in the proceeding sections. Inspection of the wave series shows that the wave field of all models agree well and the end of the ramp-up phase is clearly seen. In addition to this, the effect of the initial transient in the DLW model is seen for practically all DOFs.

Figure 32: Comparison with SOFTWIND experiment for case LC2.3: Uniform wind 11.4 m/s, wave height $H = 7.4$ m and wave period $T = 12.4$ s.

The mean aerodynamic thrust of the SIL model is higher than that of the simulated models. This also explains the higher mean tower base bending moment, although this appears to be best matched by OF. This is most likely explained by the use of the same aerodynamic model as the SIL model. In addition, this explains well the increased mean pitch observed in the experiment. The transients induced by the wave field ramp-up are clearly observed in all models and are well captured by QB and OF but are slightly overshoot in DLW due to the initial model transients. The heave is well matched apart from the DLW transient and the high OF equilibrium position.

In a realistic scenario for a below-rated operation point, a change in the platform pitch angle of a FOWT will induce aerodynamic damping due to the thrust force varying inversely to the platform direction of motion. Global aerodynamic effects such as rotor-wake interaction also affect the damping of the motion. In the experimental case the aerodynamic loads acting on the turbine were in fact predicted by the aerodynamic model of AeroDyn14 in the SIL setup. It is instructive to analyse the results keeping this in mind. The SIL aerodynamic model has been defined in such a way that dynamic inflow effects at the rotor plane are not accounted for. Therefore, these damping effects are only accounted for in the model due to changes in the instantaneous blade angle of attack induced by the rotor motion. This gives rise to an underprediction of the aerodynamic damping which would act to increase the pitch amplitude of platform motion, seen in the experimental results. This also leads to a lower amplitude of oscillating of the thrust loads, also seen in the experiments. It should also be observed that the actuation of the aerodynamic thrust force is based on the current turbine state. Keeping in mind that the actuator has a small time delay between command and response, this gives rise to a slight phase shift in the experimental time series, which can be observed in both aerodynamic loads and platform pitch motion.

The mooring line tensions appear to demonstrate similar behaviour as for the unforced cases. All mooring line tensions are slightly overpredicted by QB and OF while T1 is best matched by DLW. As was observed in previous cases, the mooring line tensions in T2 and T3 are underpredicted by DLW. This results in a reduced restoring force in surge direction and explains the increased mean surge displacement of the platform, despite the reduced aerodynamic thrust acting on the rotor. The reduced thrust seen in the DLW results is well explained by the aerodynamic comparison carried out in Section 4.5.

4.7. RESULTS WITH IRREGULAR WAVES AND TURBULENT WIND

The performance of the models shall now be investigated for two cases with an irregular wave field. As with the regular wave cases, the wave fields have been imported from the experiment and a Fourier decomposition was carried out to express the waves as a superposition of regular waves. The motion of the wave maker in the experiment was composed as a sum of sinusoidal components. A Bretschneider sea spectrum was applied in both test cases [16]. Unlike the regular wave cases investigated in the previous section, the experimental tests for the irregular waves were run for 4000 s in order to allow to provide a sufficient amount of data to carry out a statistical analysis.

In comparison with the models investigated here, it is found that after approximately 500 s, a deterministic agreement with the experimental values is not observed. This is to be expected as the models all integrate both aerodynamic and hydrodynamic loads differently, and over long time periods small deviations in the model initial conditions give rise to large deviations in the platform state. This is not observed as strongly in the regular wave cases due to the regular forcing frequency which ensures the system reaches a converged oscillation. Another important point is that the potential flow treatment applied in all models assumes that the

floater does not translate, and the reference position for the wave height is taken as the initial reference position. As the floater translates due to mean drift forces, this introduces a slight time lag in the wave excitation forces which compound over time. For these reasons, time series are shown only for the initial 400 s of the simulation to show the initial deterministic agreement. A statistical analysis has also been carried out on the experimental and model data in order to provide a quantitative comparison of the stochastic datasets. This analysis for LC3.1 includes the time range between 1000 s and 4000 s in order to ensure that the initial transient response of the models does not bias the statistical analysis. The time range considered for LC3.2 is between 500 s and 2500 s. The reduced range was necessary because the simulation with OF was stable only until 2500 s. To make sure that the comparison between the numerical codes and the experiment remained valid, only the aforementioned range was considered in the analysis.

The case LC3.1 has a significant wave height of 9.4 m and a peak spectral period of 14 s. The time series are shown in Figure 33. A number of similar observations can be made in this case with respect to the regular wave cases. The initial mean surge DOF in QB appears to be slightly underpredicted and the heave DOF appears to be slightly overpredicted. As with the regular test cases, all mooring line dynamics agree well. OF and QB again slightly overpredict all mooring line tensions. For the DLW model T1 agrees well and T2 and T3 are slightly underpredicted.

Figure 33: Comparison with SOFTWIND experiment for case LC3.1: significant wave height $H_s = 9.4$ m and peak spectral period $T_p = 14$ s.

When conducting the frequency domain analysis, it was found that the floater natural frequencies generally are within the range $f_{NF} \in [0.005 \text{ Hz}, 0.04 \text{ Hz}]$ while the wave frequencies are in the range $f_W \in [0.04 \text{ Hz}, 0.2 \text{ Hz}]$. The PSDs in the range of f_{NF} were found to be of much greater magnitude than those of the wave excitation frequencies. For this reason, the PSDs are plotted separately to improve readability. In addition, the PSD for T3 has been omitted as it is practically identical to T2.

The platform motion and mooring line PSDs for the f_{NF} frequency range are shown in Figure 34. It should be noted here that the PSD values of the experimental peaks are much lower than those for the case with turbulent wind, whereby the natural frequency range of the floater is more excited due to the frequency content of the wind field. Due to the relatively small displacements of the system and the fact that only linear wave excitation forces were used in this validation, the platform-turbine system of the numerical models can be considered to respond approximately as a linear system to the wave forcing. In this case, the response should therefore predominantly be at the wave forcing frequency. Despite this, it can be seen that the three natural frequencies of the floater have strong responses for the DLW model and the experiment. For OF, the surge peak is also seen but has a lower magnitude. The surge natural frequency peak is not captured in the QB model. It is believed that this is due to a fortuitous choice of initial conditions which have led to much smaller surge transient response. In addition to this, the OF model has an additional linear damping term, which may explain the lower response in this DoF as compared to DLW.

It is observed that in the experimental results small peaks in the surge DoF are observed at 0.012 Hz and 0.024 Hz. This corresponds to the longitudinal mode of the tank and its first harmonic. Although this has very low amplitude, due to the proximity to the surge natural frequency, resonance occurs. Equivalently, inspection of the pitch DoF demonstrates a small experimental peak at 0.17 Hz, which corresponds to the transverse mode of the tank. These modes are excited by the irregular wave generation taking place in these tests. Inspection of the PSD of the wave elevation indeed shows the small experimental peaks due to the longitudinal tank modes. In this case the transverse mode is too small relative to the longitudinal modes to be observable. For the heave DoF, all models underpredict the peak of the heave natural frequency, with DLW showing the lowest response. For the pitch DoF, the inverse behaviour is observed: DLW shows the closest response to the experimental results for the pitch natural frequency peak. The mooring line tensions are seen to be excited precisely at the natural frequencies of the system.

The response due to wave forcing in the frequency range f_W is shown in Figure 35. It can indeed be seen that all models respond to the wave forcing in the motion DOFs as expected. It is only in the pitch DoF that all numerical models slightly underpredict the response spectrum of the experiment. It is additionally observed that the amplitude response of the mooring line tensions in the experimental platform is slightly higher than predicted by the models. This is particularly true for T1 but T2 also shows a slight underprediction of from the numerical

models compared to the experiment. The lowest dynamic tension prediction comes from DLW.

Figure 34: Comparison with SOFTWIND experiment for case LC3.1: PSD for platform natural frequency range ($0.005\text{ Hz} < f_{NF} < 0.04\text{ Hz}$).

Figure 35: Comparison with SOFTWIND experiment for case LC3.1: PSD for wave frequency range ($0.04\text{ Hz} < f_w < 0.2\text{ Hz}$).

In order to identify further the statistical properties of the simulations, box plots of the considered sensors are shown in Figure 36. A brief description of the plots is given here for clarity. The upper and lower whiskers represent the 1% and 99% quantile of the data, respectively. The upper and lower bars represent the 25% and 75% quantiles, respectively.

The centre line represents the median signal and the box represents the interquartile range, i.e. the range where 50% of the data lie. It is observed that the trends seen visually in the previous cases are well captured here in the statistical analysis. In QB, the median surge along with the motion is within a relatively small range. The surge signal range for the other models aligns much better with the experimental values. This difference to the QB data might reflect the transient behaviour of the floater that was not present in the QB simulation. The heave median values in OF are seen to be above those of the experiments, in alignment with all results shown thus far. The medium pitch and quantiles are well captured by all models. The trends seen in the mooring line tensions is represented again well here, that QB and OF generally slightly overpredict line tensions, although considering the interquartile range, both numerical codes predict a smaller variation compared to the experimental values. DLW appears to underpredict T2 and T3 while predicting well the median T1 albeit with comparable interquartile range values to the other two codes. The 99% quantile of T1 agrees between the experiment, QB and OF simulations. For T2 and T3, the 99% quantiles differ, with QB showing the highest tension, followed by OF and then the experimental results.

Figure 36: Comparison with SOFTWIND experiment for case LC3.1: Box plot of median quantiles.

The final load case considers an irregular wave field with a turbulent wind field. This is representative of the majority of simulations which will be carried out in Task 2.2 of the FLOATECH project for the uncertainty quantification study. As with the previous irregular wave case, the scaled simulation length is 4000 s. The wave field in this case has a significant wave height of 5.8 m and a peak spectral period of 10.9 s. The wave field is again unidirectional and was slowly ramped up over 150 s in order to avoid a strong initial transient response. The wind field was generated with TurbSim [17] and has a mean windspeed of 18 m/s and a turbulence intensity of 17%. In comparison with the previous forced case LC2.3, at this velocity the controller is operating in the above-rated wind regime. The rotational rate of the rotor is

held at the rated value of 9.6 rpm and the blades are pitched to feather in order to reduce the aerodynamic torque and thrust loads. It should therefore be expected that the platform has a lower pitch angle than in LC2.3. Prior to discussion of the results, it is important to clarify some points. As was described in the previous test case LC3.1, it is not possible within the DLW model to specify an initial deflection and rotation of the turbine platform. This gives rise to a strong transient in the initial phases of the simulations. This transient dies out in the later stages of the simulation and it has been attempted to remove these from the statistical analysis. As mentioned earlier, the analysis time was reduced to 2000 s (500 s to 2500 s) because of numerical instabilities with the OF model.

Figure 37: Comparison with SOFTWIND experiment for case LC3.2: Turbulent wind field with wind speed 18 m/s, turbulence intensity 17%, irregular wave field with significant wave height $H_s = 5.8$ m and peak spectral period $T_p = 10.9$ s.

As with LC3.1, only the initial 400 s of the time series are shown for clarity. The time series can be seen in Figure 37. The inability to specify an initial condition for the platform, along with the controller delay described in load case LC2.3 gives rise to a stronger transient in the DLW surge results. The OF and QB results agree well with the experimental results here. Inspection of the pitch results show that the platform is constantly pitching during operation. This is easily explained by the fact that the wind field is turbulent and changes in the local velocity field give rise to a reaction of the turbine system. The average value between the experiment and the models appear to agree well. In addition, the stochastic behaviour of the mooring line tensions as caused by irregular sea state are clearly visible. The trends observed in previous tests with regards to mean line tensions are again observed here. The tower base moment appears to agree well between the codes, despite the surge motion of the floater in DLW. The aerodynamic thrust appears also to generally agree between the codes, however the

amplitude of oscillation appears to be larger in the experiment than is seen in the models. This will be further discussed below when presenting the spectral and statistical analysis.

As with the previous tests case, the spectral analysis has been separated into the natural frequency range $f_{NF} \in [0.005 \text{ Hz}, 0.04 \text{ Hz}]$ and the wave frequency range $f_w \in [0.04 \text{ Hz}, 0.2 \text{ Hz}]$ in order to simplify the analysis of the comparison. The platform motion and mooring line PSDs for the f_{NF} frequency range are shown in Figure 38. It is observed that the models all respond at the three natural frequencies of surge, heave and pitch. In comparison to the previous case, stochastic excitation caused by the turbulent wind field now introduces low-frequency excitation to the turbine-floater system. The PSD plot of the surge shows that the peak in the surge natural frequency is highest in DLW and comparable in QB, OF and the experiment. This is likely due to the initial transient seen in Figure 37 which could not be completely removed from the analysis for the DLW results.

The surge natural frequency is now very clearly seen (compare with Figure 34), as the longitudinal tank modes do not contribute significantly (relatively) for this case. The heave natural frequency is well captured by all three models and is identical to the case without wind as the thrust due to the controller does not influence the vertical motion of the floater. When the pitch DoF is considered, it can be seen that the peak in the natural frequency is well captured by all codes. It can be seen that the pitch natural frequency (compare with Figure 34) is shifted due to the influence of the aerodynamic loads and the damping effect this has. This is captured well by all models. The matching amplitude in the pitch DOF also explains well the matching peak between numerical models and the experiment in the PSD of the tower base moment. The PSD of the aerodynamic thrust loads also shows a peak in the pitch natural frequency. This is due to the varying thrust when the platform is oscillating forwards and backwards. The peak is overpredicted by all codes compared to the experiment. The mooring line tensions show two peaks, one at the surge and the other at the pitch natural frequency. The peak amplitudes are comparable between the codes and the experiment. QB and OF however underpredict the oscillation of T2 at the surge natural frequency.

The PSDs for the wave frequency range f_w are shown in Figure 39. As with the previous case LC3.1, the response due to the irregular wave field is seen clearly in all DOFs. The response in surge and heave is comparable in all numerical models to the experiment. In the pitch DoF, the OF simulations predict a response close to the experimental results while DLW and QB slightly underpredict the response. The amplitude of T1 is observed to be somewhat higher in the experiments. QB and OF show closer behaviour to the experiment, while DLW underpredicts the response. For T2 & T3, there is good agreement with between the OF simulations and the experimental results. QB slightly overpredicts the response while DLW slightly underpredicts the response. These differences are less marked though than the differences in T1 due to the smaller amplitude of oscillation of T2 and T3.

Figure 38: Comparison with SOFTWIND experiment for case LC3.2: PSD for platform natural frequency range ($0.005 \text{ Hz} < f_{NF} < 0.04 \text{ Hz}$)

Figure 39: Comparison with SOFTWIND experiment for case LC3.2: PSD for wave frequency range ($0.04 \text{ Hz} < f_w < 0.2 \text{ Hz}$).

The experimental response tower base moment is well captured by QB and OF, while DLW slightly underpredicts it. Regarding the aerodynamic thrust, QB shows the best agreement with the experiment, with OF and DLW showing lower response amplitudes. This is remarkable, since the aerodynamic model of OF and DLW is closer to the aerodynamic model used in the SIL in the experiment.

The statistical analysis of the results is shown in Figure 40. A relatively large spread of the surge motion in DLW is seen despite the removal of the first 500 s. It is also DLW that shows the highest values in the surge. The best agreement in the surge data spread is obtained by OF. The median heave for OF is again observed to be higher than for the experiment.

Figure 40: Comparison with SOFTWIND experiment for case LC3.2: Box plots of the statistical data.

The statistical values of the pitch DOF appear to agree well, however the spread of the data is seen to be somewhat larger in the experiments than is observed in the models. In addition, the 1% and 99% quantiles are larger in the experiment compared to the numerical simulations. A similar behaviour as in the previous cases is observed for the mooring line tensions. QB shows the highest values in all mooring line tensions while DLW shows the lowest. The larger pitching motions seen in the experiment may be the reason of the larger tower base bending moments also seen in the experiment. The three numerical models show a comparable spread of this sensor.

It can be observed that the statistical spread of the aerodynamic thrust in the experiments is much larger than in the numerical codes. This is again remarkable because the aerodynamics in the experiment were calculated with the SIL that used a comparable model to OF and DLW. Regardless of this, the spread of the numerical models is comparable and lower than the experiment. A reason for this difference might be the delay of the thrust actuator used in the experiment. This was not considered in the numerical simulations and might cause a lower damping of the floater pitch DoF, increasing the pitch, tower base moment and thrust oscillation amplitudes. Further investigation is needed to corroborate this hypothesis.

4.8. SUMMARY

The second turbine model investigated was the SOFTWIND 10MW FOWT, a 1:40 model scale of the DTU 10MW RWT mounted to a spar-buoy floating platform tested in the LHEEA wave basin of Ecole Centrale de Nantes. In this experiment, the full rotor is not modelled. Instead, a SIL approach was used [2]. QB was validated against the experimental results and verified against two numerical models, OF and DLW.

As with the previous tests case, initially decay tests were carried out in order to demonstrate that the models were correctly able to capture system natural frequencies, damping behaviour and equilibrium positions of the platform. It was observed in simulations that the system displayed a strong sensitivity to mooring line parameters such as mooring line length and anchoring point. Specifying the model exactly as in the experiments led to large deviations in results between codes and experiment. In order to allow a measure of model flexibility, it was decided at an early stage that the anchor positions shall be fixed, however mooring line lengths may be adjusted in order to align the results better with the experiment. These were specified in the decay tests and were then fixed for all following cases.

It was found that all three models were able to capture well the natural frequencies of surge, heave and pitch compared to the values recorded in the experimental campaign. In order to capture accurately the damping behaviour in the decay tests, it was required to add global floater quadratic and linear damping to the models in the pitch and roll DoFs. The other three DoFs: sway, yaw and roll were not investigated as these DoFs were found to be generally less excited and did not dominate floater dynamics due to the symmetries of the platform and acting forces. It was found that deviations in the mean mooring line tensions of the order of 5-10% occurred, however the dynamic behaviour of the mooring line tensions was well captured.

Following this, two cases with a regular wave field were carried out in LC2.1 and LC2.2. The experimental wave fields were imported into the models by performing a spectral decomposition of the experimental wave fields. These were then reconstructed in the models and used to calculate hydrodynamic forces. Small deviations in the hydrostatic modelling approaches were found to influence the mean heave position. In general however, the floater dynamics were well captured by the use of the LPMD approach for the calculation of hydrodynamic loads in all three models. Deviation in the mooring line tensions was also seen in these cases, analogous to the decay tests. A duplicate model was set up within QB, which included the experimental uncertainties associated with mooring line length and load cell mass, and deviations of the order seen in the simulations were recorded. It was therefore concluded that the values in the simulations of all three models are acceptable when taking experimental uncertainties into account.

In LC2.3 aerodynamic loads were allowed to act on the rotor in order to account for a fully-coupled aero-servo-hydro-elastic modelling approach. Here it was observed that small deviations in the thrust predicted by the aerodynamic models give rise to large deviations in other dynamic parameters such as the platform pitch and mooring line tensions. In general, the dynamic behaviour of the experiment was well captured by all models, however with discrepancies which generally mirrored those of the unforced cases. Inspection of the time series for loads showed that the use of the SIL model introduces a slight time lag between the aerodynamic loads and the system's response, which made reproducing the response of the system challenging in the numerical models. A possibility to improve error analysis for cases with aerodynamic forcing would be to directly import the force signal (for these tests, this is

the thrust acting at the rotor shaft) of the experiments and apply this as an external load within the simulation. This modelling option is however only available in QB. This work shall be considered for future comparisons. It must be noted that the DLW model has significant deficiencies with regard to problem setup and modelling freedom. In particular, it is not possible to define an arbitrary initial position of the FOWT. For short time series this can be problematic due to the significant influence of initial transient dynamics.

Following the regular wave tests, two tests were carried out with irregular wave fields- LC3.1 and LC3.2. The wave fields were again synthesised from the experimental campaign. In LC3.1 it was seen that platform and mooring line dynamic response were generally well captured by all three models. In LC3.2 aerodynamic forcing and a controller were included in order to simulate the fully coupled system. It was furthermore observed that the LLFVW aerodynamic model indeed leads to discernible differences in aerodynamic loading, particularly from a statistical point of view due to the variation in the representation of dynamic rotor loads. It was found that OF was subject to significant numerical instabilities for these tests cases, which required model simplification and truncation of the simulation time. The cause of these instabilities is still under investigation. A further deficiency in the DLW model is an initial time lag of the aerodynamic loads when a controller is applied. This, in addition to the initial position specification described previously, introduce very large initial transients into the simulation and require modelling workarounds for comparisons of short-time simulations.

In general, the dynamics of the model were captured in all cases at least as well by QB as the other models. In some cases, QB was found to perform better than OF and DLW. This provides adequate justification for the ongoing work on Task 2.2 of the FLOATECH project, where the uncertainty quantification of applying these models will be investigated in greater detail.

4.9. CHAPTER REFERENCES

- [1] Arnal, V., Modélisation expérimentale d'une éolienne flottante par une approche « software-in-the-loop », PhD Thesis, Ecole Centrale de Nantes, 2020.
- [2] Bak, C., Zahle, F., Bitsche, R., Kim, T., Yde, A., Henriksen, L.C., Andersen, P.B., Natarajan, A., Hansen, M.H., Design and Performance of a 10 MW Wind Turbine; Technical Report I-0092; DTU Wind Energy: Roskilde, Denmark, 2013.
- [3] Mueller, K., Lemmer, F., Yu, W., Life50Plus Deliverable D4.2 Public Definition of the two LIFES50+ 10MW Floater Concepts. Life50Plus deliverables.
- [4] Jonkman, J. Definition of the Floating System for Phase IV of OC3. Technical Report National Renewable Energy Laboratory, NREL/TP-500-47535, 2010.
- [5] Faltinsen, O. Sea Loads on Ships and Offshore Structures. Cambridge University Press. ISBN 9780521458702, 1993.

- [6] Perez-Becker, S., Behrens de Luna, R., Aero-Hydro-Elastic Model Definition in QBlade Ocean, Technical Report: Deliverable 2.1, FLOATECH Project, H2020-EU.3.3.2. – Low-cost, low-carbon energy supply EU project, 2022.
- [7] Madsen, H. A., Larsen, T. J., Pirrung, G. R., Li, A., and Zahle, F., Implementation of the Blade Element Momentum Model on a Polar Grid and its Aeroelastic Load Impact, *Wind Energ. Sci.*, 5, 1–27, <https://doi.org/10.5194/wes-5-1-2020>, 2020.
- [8] Marten, D., Implementation, Optimization and Validation of a Nonlinear Lifting Line Free Vortex Wake Module within the Wind Turbine Simulation Code QBlade., Proc. ASME Turbo Expo, Montreal, Canada, 2015. doi:101115/1.4031872.
- [9] Perez-Becker, S., Papi, F., Saverin, J., Marten, D., Bianchini, A., Paschereit, C. O., Is the Blade Element Momentum Theory Overestimating Wind Turbine Loads? – An Aeroelastic Comparison Between OpenFAST’s AeroDyn and QBlade’s Lifting-Line Free Vortex Wake Method, *Wind Energy Science* 5, 721-743, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.5194/wes-5-721-2020>.
- [10] QBlade Documentation Page, <https://docs.qblade.org/>, online, last access 11.08.2022.
- [11] Elastodyn Theory Guide and Users Manual. Readthedocs: <https://openfast.readthedocs.io/en/dev/source/user/elastodyn/index.html>. Accessed 10.08.2022.
- [12] Leishman, J.G., Beddoes, T.S., A semi-empirical model for Dynamic Stall. *Journal of the American Helicopter Society*, No. 3, Vol. 34, Pages 3-17, 1989.
- [13] Recuero, A.M., Negrut, D., Chrono Support for ANCF Finite Elements: Formulation and Validation Aspects. University of Wisconsin-Madison, Technical Report TR-2016-11, 2016.
- [14] A. Babarit, G. Delhommeau: Theoretical and numerical aspects of the open source BEM solver NEMOH. In Proc. of the 11th European Wave and Tidal Energy Conference (EWTEC2015), Nantes, France.
- [15] Borg, M., Mirzaei, M. and Bredmose, H., Wind Turbine Models for the Design, Technical Report: Deliverable D1.2 of the LIFE50+ H2020 Project. 2015.
- [16] Bretschneider, C. L. (1957). Revisions in Wave Forecasting: Deep and Shallow Water. *Coastal Engineering Proceedings*, 1(6), 3. <https://doi.org/10.9753/icce.v6.3>
- [17] Jonkman, B. J., Turbsim User’s Guide: Version 1.50. National Renewable Energy Laboratory, Technical Report NREL/TP-500-46198, 2009.

5. VALIDATION RESULTS FOR THE DTU 10 MW RWT WITH THE HEXAFLOAT SUBSTRUCTURE

This section presents the validation results of the DTU 10 MW RWT with the Hexafloat substructure, henceforth called 10 MW Hexafloat model. This novel FOWT turbine concept has a more complicated platform geometry compared to the first two turbine models presented in this report. It is therefore an important validation case to show that QB is also able to accurately model the complex geometries of the next generation of FOWTs. For this turbine model, no experimental data is available. Therefore, the validation of QB is done by code-to-code comparison with the results from the established commercial code DLW. As with the OC5 turbine, only two turbine models were compared in order to avoid superfluous results analysis in the validation of QB. For this reason, OF has been omitted from this comparison.

5.1. DESCRIPTION OF THE TURBINE MODEL

The complete description of the 10 MW Hexafloat model is given in [1]. Figure 41 shows the FOWT model in an irregular sea state. The QB model of the 10 MW Hexafloat is publicly available at the following location:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6397313>

Figure 41: 10 MW Hexafloat model within QB in an irregular sea state simulation

The QB model used in this validation study has one important difference compared to the model presented in [1]. The aerodynamic blade definition was modified so that it aligns with

the aerodynamic blade definition in Section 4. As already mentioned, this was done to align the aerodynamic blade definitions between the different aeroelastic tools and with the definition used in the SOFTWIND experiments. Careful attention was taken to align the model definitions in QB and DLW. From the modelling differences however between the codes discussed in Sections 2 and 4.2, small differences in the turbine response are expected. In particular, the differences in the aerodynamic tests between QB and DLW seen in Section 4.5 are main source of differences in the FOWT response, as will be shown in Sections 5.4 and 5.5.

In order to do validation tests with wind and waves, a controller was added to the turbine model. The ROSCO v. 2.4.1 controller was chosen as a suitable controller for this model [2]. This is because this controller includes a velocity feedback damping loop that is specially designed to increase the stability of FOWTs. For the validation cases presented here, this feature however was not enabled and the original controller parameters for the DTU 10 MW were used. The reason for this is that some difficulties were identified in the communication between ROSCO and DLW. This affected the tower fore-aft acceleration signal needed for the velocity feedback damping loop. It is expected that these difficulties will be cleared for Task 2.2 and the full capabilities of the controller will be used with all codes.

Table 9: Load Sensors for the 10 MW Hexafloat model validation.

Sensor Name	Description	Coordinate system
BR1_My	Blade 1 out of plane bending moment	Coned
TB_My	Tower base fore-aft bending moment	Tower base
Fair1_Fx – Fair3_Fx	Mooring line 1-3 tension at the fairlead position	Local
T1_My	Tank 1 Y bending moment	Local, tank 1 position
Substructure DoFs	Substructure displacements in all 6 degrees of freedom	Global
CW_CoG_X, CW_CoG_Z	Counterweight CoG X and Z position	Global
Tend1_Fx, Tend3_Fx	Tendons 1 and 3 tension at the tank connection point	Local
Rot_spd	Low speed shaft (rotor) speed	-
Pit_ang	Blade 1 pitch angle	-

A selection of load sensors have been chosen for the validation that are representative of the full FOWT system dynamics. The sensors are presented in Table 9. The coned, tower top and tower base coordinate systems are defined in [3]. The positions of the tendons 1 and 3 as well as of the tank 1 used for the substructure load sensors are shown in Figure 42.

Figure 42: Tendons 1 and 3 and Tank 1 positions for the substructure load sensors of the 10 MW Hexafloat model.

5.2. DESCRIPTION OF THE LOAD CASES

As with the other models, a series of load cases are defined to validate the modelling capabilities of QB. These load cases range from simple static tests up to simulations with turbulent wind speeds and irregular sea states. Table 10 lists all the considered load cases for the 10 MW Hexafloat model. No currents were considered for this validation. In addition, no aerodynamic tests were performed for this model since it shares the same rotor as the SOFTWIND 10 MW model. So, the aerodynamic validation carried out in Section 4.5 is also valid for this model.

5.3. RESULTS OF THE STATIC AND DECAY TESTS

The first validation test for the 10 MW Hexafloat model is the static test, or LC0.1 from Table 10. Here, only the steady, converged values of a selection of key sensors were compared. The results are shown in Table 11. It is noted that in Table 11 only the values for the substructure

are considered. The turbine sensors were previously validated in DLW and QB by comparing them to reference values. It can be seen that there is very good agreement between both codes. In most platform degrees of freedom, there is no difference in the static values. The differences in the mooring line tensions are only approximately 1.4 %. The large percentage differences in surge and pitch are explained by the relatively small absolute values of the equilibrium values. In absolute terms, a difference in surge of 0.035 m in a substructure spanning about 90 m in length can be considered negligibly small.

Table 10: Load Cases used for the 10 MW Hexafloat model validation.

Load Case Nr.	Description	Wind Condition	Wave Condition
LC0.1	Static Test	None	None
LC0.2	Surge Decay	None	None
LC0.3	Sway Decay	None	None
LC0.4	Heave Decay	None	None
LC0.5	Roll Decay	None	None
LC0.6	Pitch Decay	None	None
LC0.7	Yaw Decay	None	None
LC1.1	Reg. Wave; 1 No Wind	None	H = 9 m, T = 18 s
LC1.2	Reg. Wave 2; No Wind	None	H = 7.5 m, T = 12 s
LC1.3	Reg. Wave 1; Constant Wind	11.4 m/s; steady	H = 7.4 m, T = 12.4 s
LC2.1	Irreg. Wave 1; No Wind	None	JONSWAP, Hs = 9.4 m, Tp = 14 s
LC2.2	Irreg. Wave 2; Turb. Wind	18 m/s TI = 17%; turbulent	JONSWAP, Hs = 5.8 m, Tp = 10.9 s
LC2.3	Irreg. Wave 2; Turb. Wind	11.4 m/s TI = 15.1%; turbulent	JONSWAP, Hs = 7.7 m, Tp = 12.4 s

Table 11: Results of the 10 MW Hexafloat model static tests.

Sensor	QB	DLW	Diff [%]
Surge	0.055 m	0.02 m	175
Sway	0 m	0 m	0
Heave	-0.11 m	-0.11 m	0
Roll	0 deg	0 deg	0
Pitch	-0.215 deg	-0.2 deg	7.5
Yaw	0 deg	0 deg	0
Fair1_Fx	7.320E+05 N	7.218E+05 N	1.4
Fair2_Fx	7.315E+05 N	7.213E+05 N	1.4
Fair3_Fx	7.315E+05 N	7.213E+05 N	1.4

Figure 43 to Figure 46 show the time series of the surge, heave, pitch and yaw decay tests, respectively. It can be seen that visually there is very good agreement between both codes in all DoFs. Additionally, apart from the static offset, the mooring line tensions also agree very well. The results for the sway and roll decay tests are very similar and are not shown here for brevity.

Figure 43: Time series of the 10 MW Hexafloat surge decay test.

Figure 44: Time series of the 10 MW Hexafloat heave decay test.

Figure 45: Time series of the 10 MW Hexafloat pitch decay test.

Figure 47 shows the relative numerical values of the natural frequencies and quadratic damping for all six decay tests. Only the quadratic damping was considered since the 10 MW Hexafloat model is build using the Morison equation approach [1], which only features quadratic damping terms. It can be seen in Figure 47 that the natural frequencies of the main degrees of freedom are very similar, with the largest discrepancies of 17% in the yaw DoF. This very likely comes from the high damping of this DoF (as seen in Figure 46) which only leaves a small number of peaks to which to apply the algorithm for natural frequency and damping determination (taken from [4]). See [1] for further details. The same can be said for the quadratic damping term, where the yaw DoF shows the highest discrepancies of 13%.

Figure 46: Time series of the 10 MW Hexafloat yaw decay test

Figure 47: Relative frequencies and damping for the 10 MW Hexafloat decay tests

5.4. RESULTS WITH REGULAR WAVES AND CONSTANT WIND

The next set of load cases that were analysed are the load cases with regular waves, namely LC1.1 to LC1.3 in Table 10. With these load cases, a simple environmental disturbance is considered and the response of the system analysed.

Figure 48 and Figure 49 show the substructure displacements and the fairlead tensions of LC1.1 and LC1.2, respectively. These are the simpler cases without wind. Regarding the displacements, there is very good agreement between DLW and QB. This is true for both the mean and amplitude of the oscillations. Only for LC1.2 there is a difference in the mean surge position of 0.5 m.

Figure 48: Substructure Displacements and Fairlead Tensions for the 10MW Hexafloat LC1.1

When the fairlead tensions are considered, there are differences in the mean of the oscillations in both load cases. For the fairlead tension 1, QB shows an increase in the mean tension of about 0.2% - 0.8%, depending on the load case. For fairlead tensions 2 and 3, the mean tension is about 0.8% - 0.9% higher in QB. These values are comparable to the ones reported in the static tests and can be related to small differences in the modelling between both codes.

In addition, for LC1.2, the amplitude of the fairlead tension oscillations is also higher in QB. The amplitude of the tension oscillations for tensions 2 and 3 are about 25% higher in QB compared to DLW. It should be noted that even if this relative value seems large, it is actually small compared to the overall tension of the mooring lines. The amplitude difference represents about 5 kN, which is less than 1% of the mean tension of the mooring lines. The reason for this difference can be attributed to the slightly larger amplitude of the surge oscillation seen in QB for LC1.2.

Figure 49: Substructure Displacements and Fairlead Tensions for the 10MW Hexafloat LC1.2.

As was seen in Sections 4.6 and 4.6, the static and dynamic response of the mooring line tensions was generally underpredicted by DLW and overpredicted by QB compared to the experimental results. The different modelling approaches from both codes are again showing a similar trend in this numerical validation and should be considered in the overall evaluation of the results.

Figure 50 and Figure 51 show the additional sensors for the LC1.1 and LC1.2 cases. The additional sensors include the CW CoG, the tendon tension, the controller signals and the tower base and blade root bending moments. Similar to the results in Figure 48 and Figure 49, there is very good agreement between QB and DLW in most of the considered sensors. The two sensors that show the largest discrepancies are the CW_CoG x position for LC1.2 and the T1 M_y moment. For the CW_CoG x position in Figure 51, there is a constant offset of about 0.5 m between DLW and QB simulations. This can be attributed to the difference in surge between the models for this load case (Figure 49). For the T1 M_y signal, there is a constant offset of about 2000 kNm between the DLW and QB results. This corresponds to a relative difference of about 8.2%. This offset was also noticed in the static tests and can be linked to small model differences. Further analysis is needed to fully understand this difference.

The next step in complexity is to consider steady wind in the regular wave cases. This is done in LC1.3 and the results shown in Figure 52 and Figure 53. It can be seen that, again, there is generally good agreement between the results of DLW and QB. There are some observations to be made though. One observation is that the mean surge and pitch of the substructure is different between the codes. In particular, the mean surge in QB is about 0.3% lower than in DLW. This difference has its origin with the aerodynamic models used in both codes. QB uses the higher order LLFVW aerodynamic model while DLW uses the more traditional BEM model. If a BEM model is used in QB (noted QB BEM in the figure), a higher mean surge is obtained.

A similar observation can be made for the substructure pitch DoF. It should be noted that there are different implementations of the BEM model and that there are differences between these implementations. In QB, the BEM model is based on [5] and discretizes the rotor plane into azimuthal sections to calculate the local induction. This and other choices of the QB BEM differ from the more traditional BEM used in DLW [6]. In Section 4.5 differences in the steady thrust forces were observed between QB and DLW. The differences seen in Figure 52 and Figure 53 can also be linked back to the different aerodynamic model because all simulations used the same controller with the same parameters.

Figure 50: Additional sensors for the 10 MW Hexafloat LC1.1

Figure 51: Additional sensors for the 10 MW Hexafloat LC1.2

Figure 52: Substructure Displacements and Fairlead Tensions for the 10MW Hexafloat LC1.3

Figure 53: Additional sensors for the 10 MW Hexafloat LC1.3.

Another difference observed in Figure 53 is that the different aerodynamic models also affect the amplitude of the rotor speed oscillations. Due to the substructure pitch oscillations the relative wind speed by the rotor will not be constant and this will affect the rotor speed signal. Although the mean of the substructure pitch DoF is different in Figure 53, the amplitude of the oscillations is practically identical. For the LLFWV simulations in QB, the rotor speed oscillations show the highest amplitude, followed by the QB BEM simulations. The DLW simulations show the lowest rotor speed oscillations. The effect of this can be seen in the blade pitch angle, the blade root M_y and the tower base M_y signals. The blade pitch angle signal reacts with a lower amplitude to the changes in the rotor speed oscillations if these

oscillations have a lower amplitude. Hence, the pitch angle signal oscillations of the DLW results have the lowest amplitude, followed by the QB BEM simulations and then the QB LLFVW simulations.

This difference in blade pitch angle oscillations has a direct impact on the B1_My and the TB_My signals. As the lift force oscillations along the blade have a lower amplitude when the blade pitch angle oscillations are smaller, this will directly affect the oscillations of the thrust on the rotor and the bending moment on the blade root. This is observed in Figure 53, where the amplitudes of the BR1_My and TB_My oscillations of the DLW simulations are smaller compared to the QB BEM and QB LLFVW oscillations. It is believed that the reason for these differences in the amplitude of the rotor speed arise from the different modelling of the rotor wake memory between the codes, however further investigation is needed to corroborate this. This simple case shows clearly that one difference in the modelling approach has an effect on the dynamics and response of the full system due to the aero-hydro-servo-elastic coupling.

5.5. RESULTS WITH IRREGULAR WAVES AND TURBULENT WIND

The final set of load cases includes irregular waves with turbulent wind. These encompass load cases LC2.1 to LC2.3 and are considered as the most challenging and realistic load cases for this validation. The analysis of these load cases is done by visually analysing the time series, by comparing the time series statistics and by analysing the PSDs of the different load sensors.

Figure 54: Substructure displacements and fairlead tensions for the 10MW Hexafloat LC2.1.

LC2.1 includes irregular waves without wind. The results of the time series are shown in Figure 54 and Figure 55. It can be seen in these figures that, apart from constant offsets in several load sensors, the load signals behave very similar between both codes. The reasons for the constant offsets of the signals were already discussed in Sections 5.3 and 5.4.

Figure 55: Additional sensors for the 10 MW Hexafloat LC2.1.

The PSDs of the displacements and fairlead tensions are shown in Figure 56. This figure shows that the responses of the turbine in the frequency domain is comparable between both codes. In DLW, the turbine shows a stronger response in the heave natural frequency. In QB, the pitch DoF of the substructure and the fairlead tensions show a higher response amplitude at the wave excitation frequencies compared to the DLW results. Differences in the mooring line tensions' dynamic response between QB and DLW were also observed in Section 4.6 with QB results showing in general better agreement with the experimental data. Figure 57 shows the PSD of the additional sensors for LC2.1. It can be seen that in general, the response of the turbine to the wave excitation frequencies is higher in QB compared to DLW. But overall, these differences remain small, as can be visually corroborated in Figure 55.

Figure 56: PSDs of the displacement sensors and fairlead tensions for the 10 MW Hexafloat LC2.1

Figure 57: PSDs of the additional sensors for the 10 MW Hexafloat LC2.1

These similarities are also captured well by the statistics of the time series. Figure 58 and Figure 59 show the boxplots of the considered load sensors. The coloured area shows the interquartile range (IQR) and the whiskers the 1% and 99% quantiles, respectively. The additional circles show the outliers. It can be seen that the values of IQR and whisker length of practically all considered sensors agree between QB and DLW simulations. This indicates that, statistically, the dynamical behaviour of the turbine is practically identical between both codes.

Figure 58: Boxplots of the displacement sensors and fairlead tensions for the 10 MW Hexafloat LC2.1

Figure 59: Boxplots of the additional sensors for the 10 MW Hexafloat LC2.1

There are some differences in the extreme values though. For example for BR1_My and TB_My in Figure 59, it can be seen that the maxima of these sensors are around 17% and 50 % higher in QB compared to DLW. This can be explained by the higher substructure pitch response in QB when a large wave hits the turbine at around 970 s of simulation time (Figure 54). This load case is usually not responsible for the extreme loads of these sensors, so the values obtained in this validation report will not be representative of the actual extreme values of these sensors. Task 2.2 will consider a larger amount of design load cases that will also cover design-driving extreme events.

The next load cases to be analysed are LC2.2 and LC2.3, which represent load cases with turbulent wind conditions and irregular sea states. Figure 60 and Figure 61 show the substructure displacements and fairlead tensions for these two load cases. What can be seen in both figures is that the QB simulations show a very large oscillation in the pitch DoF. This oscillation is much less marked in the DLW simulations and it also has an effect on the surge DoF and consequently on the fairlead tensions. The additional sensors, shown in Figure 62 and Figure 63, give more information to help understand the cause of this difference.

It can be seen in these figures that the rotor speed oscillation of the QB simulations is more pronounced compared to the DLW simulations. This in turn affects the pitch controller, which responds with higher pitch angle oscillations. This behaviour had already been discussed in Section 5.4. The difference to the currently considered load cases is that the disturbance of the rotor speed is not mainly caused by the pitching of the substructure but from the incoming turbulent wind. The differences in the controller behaviour affect the rotor thrust and excite the substructure pitch DoF. Once excited, the pitch DoF couples with the blade pitch controller to create these large oscillations as the relative wind speed seen by the rotor changes with the substructure pitch motion. The controller parameters were not adjusted to compensate

this and the velocity feedback loop from the controller was disabled, so this oscillation had very little damping. Although not shown in these figures, an important disturbance that triggers the initial rotor speed oscillations is the turbulent wind. Spikes in the hub height wind speed often lead to a sharp increase in the rotor speed, which starts the aforementioned cycle.

Figure 60: Substructure displacements and fairlead tensions for the 10MW Hexafloat LC2.2

Figure 61: Substructure displacements and fairlead tensions for the 10MW Hexafloat LC2.3

This effect is much more marked in the QB simulations than in the DLW simulations. It was seen in Section 5.4 that the unsteady aerodynamics seen by the rotor lead to larger rotor speed oscillations in QB and hence to larger reactions of the pitch controller in QB. It is believed that the same mechanism is causing these large differences in turbine behaviour seen in these load cases. An observation that supports this hypothesis can be seen in Figure 61 and Figure 63 after about 1100 s of simulation time. The blade pitch angle signal returns to its

minimum value and stays at that value for about 100 s. The effect is that after this time, the substructure pitch DoF stabilizes and practically all of the sensors align for both aeroelastic codes. It is believed that the aerodynamic models used in DLW and QB are the main source of this difference. Changing the aerodynamic model in QB from LLFVW to BEM has an effect on the rotor speed-blade pitch angle-substructure pitch oscillations but it does not prevent the large substructure pitch oscillations. More research needs to be done to corroborate this and to fully understand these differences.

Figure 62: Additional sensors for the 10 MW Hexafloat LC2.2.

Figure 63: Additional sensors for the 10 MW Hexafloat LC2.3.

The qualitative description done in the previous paragraphs can be quantified by analysing the PSDs of the different sensors. Figure 64 and Figure 65 show the PSDs of the substructure

displacements and fairlead tensions for LC2.2 and LC2.3. For LC2.2, the dominant frequency for the surge and pitch DoFs as well as the fairlead tensions is the pitch natural frequency of the turbine. This is especially so for the QB simulations. For LC2.3, the dominating frequencies for the surge DoF and the fairlead tensions is the surge natural frequency. The substructure pitch DoF is dominated by the pitch natural frequency. Again, for QB simulations the surge response is much larger than the response in the DLW simulations.

Figure 64: PSDs of the displacement sensors and fairlead tensions for the 10 MW Hexafloat LC2.2.

Figure 65: PSDs of the displacement sensors and fairlead tensions for the 10 MW Hexafloat LC2.3.

When the additional sensors are considered, one obtains a similar picture. Figure 66 and Figure 67 show the PSDs of the additional sensors for LC2.2 and LC2.3, respectively. For LC2.2,

the peak in the substructure pitch natural frequency can also be found in practically most of the signals in Figure 66. This peak is much more dominating in the QB simulations compared to the DLW simulations and it overshadows the system response to the waves.

Figure 66: PSDs of the additional sensors for the 10 MW Hexafloat LC2.2

Another point to note in this figure is the peak in the BR1_My signal at the 0.16 Hz frequency. It is much more marked in QB compared to DLW. This frequency corresponds to the once-per-revolution or 1P frequency and is typically excited by wind shear or turbulence. For the turbulent wind conditions of LC2.2, it is expected that the 1P peak in the BR1_My should be more marked, as is the case with the QB simulations.

For LC2.3, it can be seen that the effect of the surge and pitch natural frequencies is less marked in the PSDs of the additional sensors. This probably comes from the fact that the large oscillations in the pitch and surge DoFs only cover about a third of the time in Figure 61. As a result, the response of these sensors on the wave excitation frequencies can be better appreciated. The response of the tendon tensions is comparable in both codes at the wave excitation frequency. When the BR1_My and TB_My are considered, it can be seen that the response of these signals at the wave excitation frequencies is larger in QB compared to DLW. Additionally, the response of the QB LLFVW simulations is larger than the QB BEM simulations.

The last analysis performed is the statistical analysis of the load sensors for both load cases. Figure 68 and Figure 69 show the boxplots of the displacements and fairlead tensions of LC2.2 and LC2.3, respectively. The trends seen in Figure 60 and Figure 61 are also reflected in the boxplots. For LC2.2, the large substructure pitch oscillations are clearly reflected in the statistics of the pitch signal and the fairlead tensions (Figure 68). This leads to a wider spread in the range of these signals. The maxima of the tensions of fairleads 2 and 3 are higher in the DLW simulation compared to the QB simulations. This is because of the higher median value of the tensions due to the higher surge deflection seen in the DLW simulations.

Figure 67: PSDs of the additional sensors for the 10 MW Hexafloat LC2.3.

For LC2.3 the interquartile range of the signals are closer between both codes (Figure 69). This is because of the larger amount of time that the QB simulations did not show the substructure pitching instability. The extreme values for some sensors such as the substructure pitch angle are still considerably larger in the QB simulations compared to the DLW simulations.

Figure 68: Boxplot of the displacement sensors and fairlead tensions for the 10 MW Hexafloat LC2.2.

Figure 69: Boxplot of the displacement sensors and fairlead tensions for the 10 MW Hexafloat LC2.3.

Figure 70 and Figure 71 show the boxplots of the additional sensors for LC2.2 and LC2.3 respectively. For LC2.2, the different behaviour of the turbines in the codes is also well reflected in the statistics of these sensors (Figure 70). The rotor speed and blade pitch angle signals show a larger spread and larger absolute extrema in the QB simulations compared to the DLW simulations. Again, the oscillations are more marked in the QB LLFVW simulations than in the QB BEM simulations. The most marked effect of this can be seen in the maxima of BR1_My and TB_My. For BR1_My, the maximum of the QB LLFVW simulations are about 24% higher than the maximum of the DLW simulations. For TB_My signal, the increase reaches 42% for the QB simulations.

Figure 70: Boxplot of the additional sensors for the 10 MW Hexafloat LC2.2.

Figure 71: Boxplot of the additional sensors for the 10 MW Hexafloat LC2.3.

Figure 71 shows that the statistics of the additional sensors for LC2.3 are also affected by the different aerodynamic behaviour of the turbine in the simulations. Again, the most notable differences are seen for the BR1_My and TB_My signals. For BR1_My, the maximum in QB simulations is about 14% higher compared to DLW simulations. For TB_My, the QB simulations show a maximum that is about 20% higher compared to the maximum seen in the DLW simulations. As Figure 67 and Figure 63 reveal, the source of these differences comes from the large substructure pitch oscillations as well as the overall higher response of the turbine to the wave excitation seen in QB compared to DLW.

It should be noted that these large differences seen in LC2.2 and LC2.3 are a product of the different aerodynamic models combined with a controller that was not tuned to operate on a floating offshore wind turbine. It is expected that the differences seen for these load cases will be considerably smaller if the controller is tuned properly. This more realistic scenario with an appropriately tuned controller will be considered in Task 2.2.

5.6. SUMMARY

The third model investigated is the 10MW Hexafloat model, for which no experimental results were available. This therefore acts as code-to-code comparison for verification of QB. As compared to the previous tests cases, the Hexafloat represents a more complicated hydrodynamic case. The platform has a more complicated geometry which is less amenable to investigation with the LPMD model. In these tests a full Morison approach is taken to model the substructure hydrodynamics.

Very good agreement in floater dynamics is observed for cases without aerodynamic forcing of the turbine, in particular for static and decay tests. This is also true for test cases with regular and irregular wave fields. These tests verify well the hydrodynamic model of QB

against DLW. When aerodynamic loads are accounted for however, the difference in the aerodynamic treatment of the two models gives rise to several different responses of the fully coupled aero-servo-hydro-elastic system. Within the QB model, the amplitude of dynamic oscillation of the turbine system near the pitch and surge oscillations are much larger than is predicted by the corresponding DLW models. It has been argued that the aerodynamic modelling, particularly together with the servo control gives rise to these differences. The magnitude of these deviations then make a statistical comparison more ambiguous.

In comparison with the other investigated turbines, the Hexafloat platform represents the most challenging from a hydrodynamics point of view. This test case therefore demonstrates that the fully-coupled system dynamics are indeed heavily dependent on modelling choices. This case therefore represents, in addition to the previous two cases, a clear justification of the investigation of the uncertainty which arises from the use of different modelling approaches. This is the primary objective of WP2 of the FLOATECH project.

5.7. CHAPTER REFERENCES

- [1] Perez-Becker, S., Behrens de Luna, R., Aero-Hydro-Elastic Model Definition in QBlade Ocean, Technical Report: Deliverable 2.1, FLOATECH Project, H2020-EU.3.3.2. – Low-cost, low-carbon energy supply EU project, 2022.
- [2] Abbas, N. J., Zalkind, D. S., Pao, L., and Wright, A., A reference open-source controller for fixed and floating offshore wind turbines, *Wind Energ. Sci.*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 53–73, Jan. 2022, doi: 10.5194/wes-7-53-2022.
- [3] Jonkman, J., Buhl, M., FAST User’s Guide, Technical Report NREL/EL-500-38230, NREL, Golden CO, USA, 2005.
- [4] Robertson A., Jonkman, J., Wendt, F., Goupee, A. and Dagher, H., Definition of the OC5 DeepCwind Semisubmersible Floating System, National Renewable Energy Lab, University of Maine.
- [5] Madsen, H. A., Larsen, T. J., Pirrung, G. R., Li, A., and Zahle, F., Implementation of the Blade Element Momentum Model on a Polar Grid and its Aeroelastic Load Impact, *Wind Energ. Sci.*, 5, 1–27, <https://doi.org/10.5194/wes-5-1-2020>, 2020.
- [6] Principia and IPF Energies Nouvelles, AeroDeeP 2.2 Theory Guide, January 2021.

6. CONCLUSIONS

In this work QB, an innovative tool for aero-hydro-servo-elastic simulation of floating wind turbines, is benchmarked against experimental data and two other state-of-the-art numerical codes. Verification is performed on three test cases, each based on a different concept of floating substructure; a semi-submersible, a spar-buoy and Hexafloat, an innovative two-part floater concept proposed by Saipem. As experimental results existed for the OC5 and SOFTWIND models, validation tests are also performed. For each test case, the numerical models used for the verification are set-up and calibrated using a series of simplified tests, such as static equilibrium tests and free decay tests. QB's ability to capture increasingly complex physical phenomena is then tested by gradually increasing the complexity of the test runs. In fact, models are compared in regular wave tests, irregular wave tests with no wind and combined irregular wind and wave tests. Overall, the outcome of the verification and validation exercise has been successful in all three test cases. As detailed throughout this document however, there are some points of note for each of the test cases that will be summarized in the following.

The first test case is the 5 MW OC5 FOWT model, a 1:50 scale model wind turbine mounted on a semi-submersible type platform, described in full detail in Section 3. QB is compared to experimental data and to OF. Both numerical models are set up with similar modelling choices in mind: A Linear-Potential flow with Morison Drag (LPMD) approach is used to model hydrodynamics, second-order hydrodynamic excitation is accounted for in both models through a quadratic transfer function and an explicit mooring line model is used to model the mooring cables. OF and QB also share the same inputs in terms of the radiation and diffraction coefficients and of airfoil aerodynamic coefficients. Very good agreement is noted between the numerical models and experiments in decay tests.

In regular wave tests, better agreement with experiments was noted when wave time series from the basin tests are used as input to the numerical models. In fact, as the waves generated in the basin are not perfectly sinusoidal, a spectral analysis of the signal revealed the presence of higher-order harmonics, exciting system frequencies other than the wave frequency.

In irregular wave tests with no wind the ability to accurately predict experimental results is noted. From a visual comparison, the response of the various load sensors is well in-phase even several minutes into the test-runs. A statistical analysis revealed an underprediction of low-frequency platform response caused by the excitement of the system's natural frequencies. This also led to underestimations in the 99% quantiles of tower base fore-aft shear force and bending moments of about 25-20%. As noted in [1] this is due to higher-order wave hydrodynamic effects, for which including second-order excitation is not sufficient. The response of QB is in line with OF and with the general performance of the codes tested in the OC5 campaign [1].

The full coupled system response to wind and wave constitutes the final step. In these conditions QB was able to capture excitation due to turbulent wind – both at rated wind speed and above rated wind speed – very well. Underestimation of tower base loads remain due to the higher-order hydrodynamic effects noted in irregular waves tests. Underestimation can be considered small, ranging between 4% and 15% depending on the specific metric and wind/wave condition. Overall QB performed as well or better than the state-of-the-art code OF in these conditions.

The second test case is the SOFTWIND 10MW FOWT, a 1:40 model scale of the DTU 10MW RWT mounted to a spar-buoy support structure tested in the LHEEA wave basin of Ecole Centrale de Nantes. QB is benchmarked with respect to experimental data and two other state-of-the-art simulation tools, OF and DLW. In the experiment, the full rotor is not modelled, instead a software-in-the-loop approach is used [2]. This approach introduces a slight time-lag between the aerodynamic loads and the system's response, which made reproducing the exact response of the system challenging in the numerical models. Moreover, experimental uncertainties are present especially in mooring line tensions, as changes in mean values of these load-sensors are noted between test campaigns. The numerical models also showed a strong dependency on the exact mooring line configuration (anchor position, mooring line length).

After significant tuning of the numerical models, all three were able to capture well experimental decay test, regular and irregular wave tests. Some of the parameters that were tuned in the numerical models can be listed as follows: i) mooring line length – in the experiment length were measured with no tension applied, which could stretch the lines ii) buoyancy and system weight were adjusted within experimental uncertainties to match static heave position iii) additional hydrodynamic damping as required to match experimental decays. It must be noted that the DLW model has significant deficiencies with regard to problem setup and modelling freedom. In particular, it was not possible to define an arbitrary initial position of the FOWT. For short time series this can be problematic due to the significant influence of initial transients on spectral behaviour.

In tests with irregular wind and waves, statistical variations in rotor loads in unsteady wind are discernible when using LLFVW (QB) as compared to other BEM-style models (DLW, OF). While QB compares well to experimental data, comparison with OF and DLW have shown some deficiencies in the latter models. In particular, the inability to specify adequate initial conditions in terms of platform position and rotor operating point (rotor speed, blade pitch), influence the results from DLW. OF on the other hand is affected by numerical instability, which prevented the completion of the irregular wind and waves case. The instability is only noted in irregular waves and wind runs, and seems to be related to the LPMD approach. The issue could not be solved in the timeframe of this task. Only partial comparisons of QB to the other numerical models were possible in these conditions.

The third model is the 10MW Hexafloat model. For this turbine model, no experimental data is available. Therefore, the verification of QB is done by code-to-code comparison with the results from the established commercial code DLW. In this test case, the turbine is supported by a complex two-part substructure that is modelled with a Morison approach in both codes. Very good agreement between numerical codes is seen when wind is not included in the test. In particular, excellent agreement in static and decay tests is noted as well as excellent agreement in regular wave cases without wind. Some small differences in surge and the tank 1 bending moment are observed. Very good agreement is also observed in the irregular wave without wind load case.

Differences are seen when wind is included in the tests. For regular waves with wind, differences in the aero model between DLW and QB lead to differences in several turbine and controller sensors due to the aero-servo-hydro-elastic coupling of the model. In the irregular waves with turbulent wind cases, large differences are seen in the turbine response. In particular, the turbine sees high amplitude oscillations in the pitch and surge natural frequencies when simulated with QB. It is argued that the different aerodynamic models in QB and DLW are the source of this difference. These large oscillations overshadow the rest of the turbine response and make a statistical comparison difficult. A correct tuning of the controller is expected to mitigate this problem.

In summary, QB was able to reproduce the experimental behaviour of the 5MW OC5 model and 10MW SOFTWIND model and is in good agreement with DLW in the 10MW Hexafloat test case. For all three simulated models, excellent agreement is noted between the codes and the experiments (where present) in tests without wind. Where comparisons to experiments could be made, an underestimation of natural-frequency excitation in irregular waves is noted. This may be attributed to either an underestimation of the low frequency wave loads or an underestimation of damping. Results from QB appear to be in line with other state of the art codes. When wind loads are introduced, excellent agreement is noted in the NREL 5MW OC5 model, while discrepancies arise between QB and the other BEM-based codes in the other test cases. It must be noted that no blade pitch or rotor torque control is present in the NREL 5MW OC5 model. For both the SOFTWIND model and particularly the 10MW Hexafloat model, small differences in aerodynamic response give rise to deviating controller responses. These naturally give rise to further deviations in the turbine response and for long simulations a significant influence on the statistical content of the turbine loads may be observed. These deviations are somewhat to be expected and are in fact the main objective of the investigations into the effect of higher order modelling differences within WP2 of the FLOATECH project. The work carried in this report acts not only to validate QB, but also to demonstrate that further detailed investigation is required, particularly of a statistical nature in order to accurately quantify the uncertainty associated with the use of higher-order modelling approaches. In conclusion, given the outcomes of this work, the validation exercise is considered successful.

6.1. CHAPTER REFERENCES

- [1] Robertson, A. et al., OC5 Project Phase II: Validation of Global Loads of the DeepCwind Floating Semisubmersible Wind Turbine, 14th Deep Sea Offshore Wind R&D Conference, EERA DeepWind'2017, Trondheim, Norway, 2017 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2017.10.333>.
- [2] Arnal, V., Modélisation expérimentale d'une éolienne flottante par une approche « software-in-the-loop », PhD Thesis, Ecole Centrale de Nantes, 2020.